

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D1.1 Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
5G	5th generation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AGV	Automatic Guided Vehicle
AR	Augmented Reality
BTS	(2G) Base Tranceiver Station
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System
E2E	End To End
ECU	Electronic Control Unit
eMBB	enhanced Mobile BroadBand
ERTMS	European Rail Traffic Management System,
EU	European Union
FRMCS	Future railway mobile Communication System
GPS	Global Positionning System
gNB	next Generation Node B
GSM-R	Global System for Mobile Communication - Railways
ICS	Intersection Controller System
IMU	Immersive Multi User
IoT	Internet Of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
MEC	Mobile Edge Computing
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
Node B	3G BTS
NRT	Non Real Time
OBU	On Board Unit
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RRM	Radio Resource Management
RSU	Road Side Units
RT	Real Time
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SPaT	Signal Phase and Timing
TMC	Traffic Management Center
UC	Use Case
UCC	Use Case Category
UHD	Ultra High Definition

UIC	Union Internationale de Chemin de Fer / International Union of Railways
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
UTC	Universal Time Coordinated
V2D	Vehicle-to-device
V2G	Vehicle-to-grid
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2N	Vehicle-to-network
V2P	Vehicle-to-pedestrian
V2V	Vehicle-to-vehicle
V2x	Vehicle-to-everything
VR	Virtual Reality
VRU	Vulnerable Road User

Executive Summary

This report provides a representative set of detailed use case scenarios for Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) with appropriate requirements to be tested and validated both in lab and in large-scale field trials across borders. The document summarizes the work done by the partners to define use cases, scenarios and KPIs applicable to 5G Connected and Automated Mobility trials. 5G-ROUTES stakeholders come from different companies and have a different background and interest in the project. We have first analysed their characteristics and identified 4 categories of stakeholders: The telecom category contains large telecom manufacturers and operators; within the transport category, railway operators are supporting future railway mobile communications system (FRMCS); Several SMEs, Research institutes and universities bring their expertise on specific domains.

5G will extend the range of services offered by mobile telecom systems. Three directions have been identified by ITU-R: massive Machine Type Communications, Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications and enhanced Mobile BroadBand communication. We have detailed the multilayer architecture of a 5G radio access network and some key features of the core network as Mobile Edge Computing, Network Slicing and roaming. Finally, we described typical satellite communication systems and detailed the performance of different 4G, 5G, satellite and 5G-ROUTES experimental network.

Several use cases of CAM using 5G networks have been identified in the 5G-ROUTES project. We have identified key aspects of these use cases and filed them in 3 main categories: The mMTC category groups messaging applications which involve a large number of devices; the URLLC category groups real time applications with strong delay constraints; the eMBB category groups use cases which require high data rates. These use cases and their requirements are further described in more details, as well as the corresponding scenarios.

The work carried out showed that the performances of 5G networks are sufficient but necessary to support our use cases; it shows also that the selected use cases exploit all the possibilities of 5G networks.

This document is the initial version of the CAM use cases and will be updated by month M10.

1 Introduction

The 5G-ROUTES project aims to conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CAM applications seamlessly functioning across the “Via Baltica-North” 5G cross-border corridor spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitised motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe. The definition of innovative use cases is an essential step to develop and exploit CAM service over automotive, railway and maritime platform in the cross-border context.

The present deliverable aims to provide a representative set of detailed use case scenarios for CAM with appropriate requirements to be tested and validated both in lab and in large-scale field trials across borders.

The evaluation of such use cases in the 5G-ROUTES tests facilities and setup also need to be performed with respect to clearly defined KPIs. Hence, this deliverable will provide as set of technical, service level and business KPIs for proper test and demonstration of the use cases and the validation of the infrastructure.

As output of T1.1, this deliverable will provide inputs to other tasks of WP1 and other WPs, regarding the use cases description and requirements to consider in the frame of those tasks and WPs. The work done in this deliverable will be the basis for the further specification of test best, selection and configuration of use case and results analysis.

1.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES’s Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1 . Adherence to 5G-ROUTES’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D1.1 Use cases, scenario, specs & target KPIs for 5G CAM	Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0	Chapter 2, 3, 4,5,6, 7 Annex II	<p>Chapter 2 details the services and architecture of 5G and satellite networks</p> <p>Chapter 3 defines the 3 categories of Use Cases and describes 5G-ROUTES Use Cases</p> <p>Chapter 4 will describe the test facilities</p> <p>Chapter 5 will describe the test scenarios</p> <p>Chapter 6 will describe the KPIs</p> <p>Chapter 7 details the responsibility of the partners</p> <p>Annex II details the main external</p>

		stakeholders of 5G-ROUTES	
TASKS			
<p>T1.1 Definition and detailed analysis of CAM use cases, scenarios, specifications for technological enablers and target KPIs (technological and business)</p>	<p>The aim of this task is to capture the requirements from the end-user CAM stakeholders, including the articulation of detailed use case scenarios and usability needs, and relevant target technological and business KPIs, which will be validated in the field trials.</p> <p>Integrated satellite/terrestrial architectures and interfaces between traffic flow from satellite operator and MNO core network will also be defined in this task.</p> <p>This task will be divided into two key sub tasks:</p> <p>(a) systematic compilation of current use cases features and capabilities</p> <p>(b) requirements analysis.</p> <p>A requirement capture will involve the documentation of CAM end-users needs and opinions about new innovative vertical use cases that require 5G performance capabilities in the domains of automotive, railways, transport & logistics, IoT and infotainment.</p> <p>Such use cases will be mapped to specific target KPI and SLA values (e.g. throughput, mobility, latency, density, reliability, positioning accuracy, coverage, service provisioning time, QoS, QoE, etc.), which will set the baseline for conducting the actual measurements during the field trials.</p>	<p>Chapter 3, 4, 5 6</p>	<p>The systematic compilation of current use cases features, and capabilities is done in chapter 3</p> <p>The requirement analysis, including end users' needs, will lead to the definition of the test facilities, test scenarios and KPIs (subtask b)</p>

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 and 2 are a general introduction on 5G and the 5G-ROUTES project. Key aspects of 5G networks: services, radio access architecture, core network architecture as well as the 5G-ROUTES partner involvement are presented.
- Chapter 3 defines use case categories and details Use Cases that take advantage of 5G technologies; identifies the scenarios and relevant KPIs.
- Chapter 4 and 5 details the test facilities and tests that will be conducted to assess the KPIs.
- Chapter 6 details the characteristics of the technical, service and business KPIs that will be assessed and monitored during the project.
- Chapter 7 details the responsibility and point of contact for each partner.
- Chapter 8 concludes the report.
- Chapter 9 lists the references used in this document.
- Annex II presents 5G-ROUTES external stakeholder in the automotive and standardization domain.

1.3 5G-ROUTES internal stakeholders

The objective of 5G-ROUTES is to assess the benefits of 5G for CAM applications under realistic conditions. Local and large field trials will be conducted in the Baltic north corridor.

Table 1 shows the activities of the 5G-ROUTES partners. See also Annex I for partners responsibilities mapping.

Table 2. 5G-ROUTES internal stakeholders

Company	ID	Telecom		Transport			SME	Research	
		Manufacturers	Operators	Rail	Ship	Automotive		University	Research institute
ERICSSON EESTI AS	EEE	X							
AIRBUS DEFENCE AND SPACE GMBH	ADS	X							
AIRBUS DEFENCE AND SPACE SAS	ADSF	X							
AKCIJU SABIEDRIBA PASAZIERU VILCIENS	PV			X					
ATOS SPAIN SA	ATOS						X		
BRAINSTORM MULTIMEDIA SL	BRA						X		
CENTRE TECNOLÓGIC DE TELECOMUNICACIONS DE CATALUNYA	CTTC								X
EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED	eBOS						X		
EESTI RAUDTEE AS	EVR			X					
ENIDE SOLUTIONS .S.L	ENIDE						X		
ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH								X
INLECOM INNOVATION ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	ILS						X		
INSTITUT VEDECOM	VED								X
IQUADRAT INFORMATICA SL	IQU						X		
LATVIJAS MOBILAIS TELEFONS SIA	LMT		X						
SWARCO MIZAR SRL	SWM						X		
TALLINNA TEHNIKAULIKOOL	TTU							X	
Teknologian tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy	VTT								X
TELIA EESTI AS	TELIA		X						
VEDIAFI OY	VEDIA						X		
WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION	WINGS						X		
Institute of Electronics and Computer Science	EDI						X		

The following details the internal stakeholder activities and interest.

1.3.1 Telecom

1.3.1.1 Manufacturers

- **Ericsson**

Ericsson is a global leader in delivering ICT solutions. In fact, 40% of the world's mobile traffic is carried over Ericsson networks with customers in more than 180 countries and comprehensive industry solutions ranging from Cloud services and Mobile Broadband to Network Design and Optimization.

Ericsson is interested in real output of field trials, to gain knowledge and experience about requirements which are set to the 5G network infrastructure by different use cases.

- **Airbus Defence and Space**

Airbus Defence and Space is manufacturing terrestrial and space telecommunication systems and is involved in 5G standardization at 3GPP and ETSI. The space division builds earth observation, navigation and telecommunication satellites for more than 30 years.

Airbus Defence and Space is interested by the development of 5G systems both in the terrestrial and space domain, in particular in the mMTC and eMBB domains.

- **ATOS**

ATOS SPAIN SA (ATOS) is a global leader in digital transformation with over 110,000 employees in 73 countries and annual revenue of over €11 billion. European number one in Cloud, Cybersecurity and High-Performance Computing, the Group provides end-to-end Orchestrated Hybrid Cloud, Big Data, Business Applications and Digital Workplace solutions. The group is the Worldwide Information Technology Partner for the Olympic & Paralympic Games and operates under the brands Atos, Atos Syntel, and Unify.

ATOS role in the project is devoted to the integration and participation in the development of the 5G technological enablers, more concretely to AI-based network slicing, and cross-domain orchestration APIs that will be validated for the use cases in a cross-border multi-operator orchestration environment

1.3.1.2 *Operators*

- **TELIA**

Telia Estonia Ltd is part of Telia Company and is the biggest telco operator in Estonia, providing fixed, wireless and IT services to both private and business customers.

Telia has been the first mobile operator to launch all the mobile generations in Estonia – including 5G. Telia is interested in gaining knowledge and practical experience with 5G and searching for commercially viable tested use cases.

- **LATVIJAS MOBILAIS TELEFONS SIA (LMT)**

LMT is a mobile telecommunications operator and market leader in Latvia, currently amongst the most efficient mobile data networks in the world. As a mobile tech innovator backed by 27 years of history, LMT brings expertise to successful collaborations with the government, academic and start-up ecosystem partners. LMT has successfully built solutions based on cutting-edge wireless technology providing the most extensive communications and data network in Latvia boasting more than 1,200 base stations. LMT was the first operator to offer 2G, 3G, 4G in Latvia and on September 2018 LMT in cooperation with Nokia and Intel demonstrated first live test of a 5G network, commercial launch was carried out in July 2019 in 3.6 GHz band.

1.3.2 **Transport**

- **EESTI RAUDTEE AS <EVR>**

Eesti Raudtee or EVR is the national railway infrastructure company of Estonia. It owns a network of 691 kilometres (429 mi) of broad gauge (1,524 mm (5 ft)) railway throughout the country, including the 192 kilometres (119 mi) used by the Elron commuter trains around Tallinn. Its sole shareholder is the Government of Estonia.

- **AKCIJU SABIEDRIBA PASAZIERU VILCIENS <PV>**

Pasažieru vilciens ("Passenger train", abbreviated: PV) is the only passenger-carrying railway company in Latvia, operating both electric and diesel trains on various lines throughout the country. It was formed in November 2001 by bringing together two separate companies, PPU "Elektrovilciens" ("Electric Train") and PPU "Dīzeļvilciens" ("Diesel Train"), under one name, creating the first subsidiary of Latvian Railways (Latvijas dzelzceļš). As of October 2008 JSC "Pasažieru vilciens" is an independent state-owned company. As of 2017, the company employed 1,075 people.[1]

PV currently operates ten routes (four electric, six diesel) with its main operating base being the capital city, Riga.

1.3.3 SME

- **BRAINSTORM MULTIMEDIA SL**

Brainstorm is a company specialized in providing advanced solutions for the creation of real-time 3D graphics and virtual studios for broadcast applications, cinema and corporate presentations that has more than 2,500 installations worldwide since its foundation in 1993.

In 5G- ROUTES, BRA will focus in providing the required server software and smart devices apps related to the use cases 4.1 and 4.2, contributing to the integration of these systems, their validation, demonstration and finally their testing.

Brainstorm is interested in the latest 3GPP releases in 5G infrastructure support for the delivery of innovative services that may require 5G performance capabilities.

- **EBOS Technologies Ltd**

EBOS Technologies Ltd is an SME company established and operating in Cyprus, with a 15th year of experience and participation in EU R&D projects, especially on the technological and development part as well as leading the overall quality of the project's outputs. Apart from the participation in EU R&D projects, EBOS also has a department dedicated to commercial solutions such as Enterprise Resource Planning, Anti Money Laundering and Risk Assessment.

One of the main strategies and commercial goals of EBOS is to utilize the gained knowledge on latest technologies, during the participation in R&D projects, into the commercial solutions of the company. More specific, in 5G-ROUTES, EBOS will utilize the knowledge gained from the 5G-SOLUTIONS project in the dashboard implementation, along with the innovative components (such as simulation and widgets concept) and make them part of Tenant Web Portal that is planned to be implemented.

- **ENIDE SOLUTIONS .S.L**

ENIDE is an SME specialized in offering consulting services, developing and combining innovative IT solutions and technologies, as well as research support services such as innovation management and use cases coordination. In detail, ENIDE's areas of expertise include **Automotive, Personal mobility, Logistics** and **Smart technology** from **Innovation** point of view.

ENIDE will integrate in its service portfolio the know-how from their participation as IT developer and business innovation experts for novel CAV business models in several CAM use cases. ENIDE intends to create a CAV technological and consultancy service targeting existing and new customers in the automotive industry as well as road operators two years after the project conclusion.

- **INLECOM INNOVATION ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA <ILS>**

Inlecom has established its reputation for excellence in Project Management and Project Delivery in the Design and Development of Advanced Solutions for Digital Transformation. Over the years, Inlecom employees have guided and consulted across dozens of successful projects and solutions in Cloud, On-Premise and Hybrid Cloud for SMEs, Enterprises and Public Sector Organizations across Europe – including domains such as Big Data, ICT,

Security, IoT, eLearning, Cognitive Computing, Transport & Logistics, Smart Cities, Circular Economy & Industrial Economics. The team has also a substantial expertise in EU and US Patent filings, IP Protection and Innovation management, and relationships with IP attorneys in Europe and USA.

- **VEDIAFI OY**

Vediafi is a Finnish company devoted to enabling **smarter and greener logistics**. Since 2013 we have been working with state-of-the-art technologies to make cross-border logistics, mobility and transport more efficient and transparent. Our solutions are based on Corridor as a Service (CaaS) -approach, which bundles the best products and services into customer friendly packages. With support of Business Finland, CaaS Nordic ecosystem and EU we enable efficient and more sustainable logistics for end-users, logistics service providers and authorities.

Vedia is interested to develop new 5G based solutions and accurate positioning to enhance the transparency and connectivity of logistics, in particularly in the IoT device and mMTC domains.

- **WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IKE**

WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS (WINGS) is an SME, which focuses on the development of solutions (software and hardware) for various vertical areas. The areas are utilities (water, energy, gas), smart/digital/liveable cities (air quality, the transportation infrastructure and buildings, parking and user mobility, and citizen security/safety), food security/safety (safety of meat/milk/oil, smart aquaculture, etc.), and, more recently, industry/logistics. The foundation for the solutions comprises IoT technologies, advanced wireless networks (4G, WiFi, 5G, etc.), cloud and big data platform, artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms, and security mechanisms (such as blockchain, distributed ledgers, etc.).

In 5G-ROUTES will lead the development of E2E slicing mechanisms and spectrum and resource allocation mechanisms for cross-border environments and based on its expertise WINGS will also significantly contribute to the creation of the validation and testing framework, while engaging in lab-testing and field-trials of its solutions in cross-border environments.

- **SWARCO MIZAR SRL**

SWARCO MIZAR SRL (SWM) is a leader company in the field of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS). The company has over twenty-five years of experience in ITS and is specialized in the research, design, development and the implementation of integrated telematics systems and services for the supervision, monitoring and control of traffic and transport. SWM operates in the market offering technologically advanced systems and services to the customer and supplying software and components to companies of the SWARCO group and international OEMs.

In 5G-ROUTES, SWM is interested in integration and assessment of an innovative ITS technology in the Estonia Pilot site, as an early adopter of the 5G technology for traffic management applications. In specific, in the development of use-cases for a safe (vulnerable road users' identification and alarms) and optimized intersection (adaptive multi-modal traffic control).

- **Iquadrat Informatica (IQU)**

Iquadrat Informatica is an SME which is delivering a new generation of tools and platforms for system-level evaluation of wireless integrated communication systems, with a strong focus on 5G. Our R&D activities have a strong focus in Software-Defined Networking (SDN), Network Function Virtualisation (NFV) and Network Slicing.

The innovative technological advancements for AI-based dynamic network slicing will be embedded in IQU evaluation tools for enhancing the existing product portfolio and testing platforms for 5G wireless networks.

1.3.4 Research

1.3.4.1 University

- **Tallinna Tehnikaülikool <TTU>**

Tallinn University of Technology (TTU), is the only technological university in Estonia and is the flagship of Estonian engineering and technology innovation and education. In 5G-ROUTES, Thomas Johann Seebeck Department of Electronics and particularly its communication systems research group is involved in various national and international projects funded by EC, NATO-SPS, Estonian Research Council etc.

TTU, is leading WP2 (technology enabler), UC3.2. TTU is interested in 5G-NR based positioning and radio slicing as well as for developing its testbed capabilities with side link V2X and connected maintenance (for both mMTC and URLLC domains).

1.3.4.2 Research institutes

- **Teknologian tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy**

VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd is a state owned and controlled non-profit limited liability company established by law and operating under the ownership steering of the Finnish Ministry of Employment and the Economy. VTT is impact-driven and takes advantage from its wide multi-technological knowledge base to strengthen Finnish and European industrial competitiveness.

In 5G-ROUTES, VTT will engage research teams Automated vehicles and Autonomous systems connectivity. VTT is performing research in automated driving technologies for automotive and work machine industry domains, as well as in 5G network applications. VTT has a set of research prototype vehicles which have autonomous driving capabilities and are used for testing innovative use cases. VTT is also involved in several 5G test network related activities in Finland.

- **CENTRE TECNOLÒGIC DE TELECOMUNICACIONS DE CATALUNYA**

The Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC) is a private non-profit R&D center financed by the region of Catalunya with research and development partnerships with industry. The Smart Energy Efficient Communication Technologies (SMARTECH) Department, part of the Communications Technologies Division (CTD) conducts fundamental and experimental research activities on technologies related to WSNs, WLANs and dense cellular networks

CTTC is interested in AI assisted cross-domain MEC and integration fabric for CAM services, will provide its 5G testbed for lab trials and will lead the dissemination and communication effort.

- **ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS (CERTH)**

The Center for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is one of the largest research centres in Greece founded in 2000. The mission of CERTH is to promote the triplet **Research – Development – Innovation** by conducting high quality scientific research and developing innovative products and services (www.certh.gr).

In 5G-ROUTES, CERTH involves one of its 5 institutes, the **Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT)**. CERTH/HIT is the Greek National Institute for the promotion of Transport Research and Policy support. It focuses on applied research in all fields and modes of Transport (www.hit.certh.gr).

CERTH/HIT key expectations in 5G-ROUTES project include the extension of its research competence in the fields of a) communication algorithms and b) prototyping of interaction strategies for connecting all traffic participants and especially VRUs (pedestrians, cyclists, motorcyclists). In addition, it targets to create a spin-off company to deploy the OBU hardware and the associated algorithms for VRU multi-communication, including

5G. Lastly, CERTH/HIT expects to advance its long experience on business evaluation and impact assessment methods and tools, adapted specifically for 5G ecosystems.

- **Institute of Electronics and computer science <EDI>**

EDI was founded in 1960 within the framework of the Latvian Academy of Sciences and is currently a state research institute conducting fundamental and applied research in following Latvian Smart Specialization Strategy (RIS3) areas: “Information and Communication Technologies” and “Intelligent Materials, Technologies and Engineering Systems”, and scientific priority directions:

- **INSTITUT VEDECOM<VED>**

VEDECOM was created in February 2014 and is an Institute for Energy Transition (ITE) established as part of the French government’s ‘Investment for the future plan’ (Programme d’Investissements d’Avenir or PIA). This Institute responds to the challenges of the autonomous vehicle and the mobility in the future. The aim of VEDECOM is to develop disruptive technologies and a cross-disciplinary vision of new usages, for sustainable, safe, efficient and affordable mobility.

2 5G Generalities

The following paragraphs details the range of 5G services and typical aspects of 5G network architecture.

2.1 Services

Figure 1. 5G service (source ITU)

With the deployment of 5G networks, mobile services will benefit from higher throughput, lower latency and higher reliability. This in turn will favor the emergence of new services. These services have been classified by ITU in three main categories:

- massive Machine Type Communication (mMTC);
- enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB);
- Ultra-reliable and low latency communications (URLLC).

Furthermore, the evolution of mobile core networks enables to support the following vertical markets:

- mobile communications;
- transportation (vehicle, railways, maritime, aeronautical);
- smart cities;
- smart home building;
- the Internet of Things.

In 5G-ROUTES, we will present various use cases that take advantage of 5G network characteristics. These use cases fall into the following categories:

- automated cooperative driving;
- awareness driving;
- sensing driving;
- uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go;
- multimodal services.

2.2 Architecture

The following subsections detail some of the important aspects of 5G radio and core network architectures.

2.2.1 Radio Access network

2.2.1.1 *Multilayer cellular coverage*

All 5G applications use radio frequencies to communicate. A key aspect of modern radio communication systems is the capability to reuse the same radio resource in different cells. A global coverage is obtained through association of several cells. The frequency reuse factor determines how often a frequency is reused. Typical values range from 7 to 1 for CDMA systems. We can differentiate several types of cells:

- **Macro cells** which enable radio coverage from a few hundred meters to few kilometres for cellular systems and thousands of kilometres for satellite-based systems. Macro cellular networks provide outdoor and indoor services. A global coverage is provided via access and core network mobility features (handover). Typical examples of macro cell networks are cellular or satellite networks. Macro cells are used for rural and urban environments.
- **Micro cells** enable radio coverage from a few meters to hundreds of meters. Micro cell networks are mainly used to provide indoor services with little to no mobility. They usually provide a higher throughput than macro cellular networks. Typical examples of micro cellular networks are DECT or WiFi networks. Microcells are also used outdoor in dense urban environments.
- **Nano cells** enable radio coverage from a few centimetres to a few meters. They are mainly used to provide short range point to point services. Mobility is not supported. A typical example of a nano cell network is a Bluetooth network.

Depending on the CAM application constraints, the radio access may be implemented with nano, micro or macro cells. The combination of multiple type of cells enables to extend and secure CAM applications and take advantage of low latency communication.

- Macro cells for global coverage
- Micro for low latency and throughput
- Nano cells for very low latency applications

The user traffic carried over the 5G network may contain simple state information (mMTC), critical information (URLLC) and high-definition video (eMBB). The signalling traffic includes registration and mobility management of the user. In general, the integration in 5G networks opens the door to new applications and services stemming from the internet realm.

5G CAM radio access architecture

Figure 2. 5G CAM radio access architecture

5

Figure 2 shows a general CAM telecom architecture.

Camera, radar and lidar sensor system are used to acquire a better knowledge of the car's environment. Part of this information can be transmitted to other cars using nano, micro or macro cells.

- A nano cell (in yellow) is established between the first and the second car. Each car has a short-range transmitter and receiver. A point-to-point communication is established between the two and sensor information as well as car related information (e.g. Identification) can be exchanged. Each car can be master of the communication. This nano cell provides very short latencies but may be affected by the distance between the two cars (communication is lost when the car is too far from each other).
- A micro cell (in green) or bubble is created by one of the cars. This cell provides a mean to exchange information while moving. Each register to the master car which forwards the information to the destination car. This micro cell provides low latency and has a limited range. In 5G network, the micro cell can be integrated in a 5G network to offer more services, like traffic information to the group.
- Terrestrial macro cells (in blue and pink) offer a global coverage for CAM services. Each car is connected to the network and information exchanged between cars transit through the network, over gNB 1 and gNB 2. In general, the traffic transits over the core network up to an application server located on the internet which dispatches the relevant information to the cars. Typical information is the sensor information plus additional data coming from the internet.
- To reduce the latency and optimize the bandwidth, it is possible to process data locally using a MEC server. The MEC server is a particular application server located near the gNB that can compress data and relay data locally without crossing the core network.
- Satellite macro cells (in Grey) over a worldwide coverage. They can be used in cross border situation and in underserved areas like seas, mountains or in cross border situations.

Table 3 details the type of cells for the different use cases

Table 3. Radio access type per service

ID	Title	Large macro (Satellite)	Macro	Micro	Nano	Comment
1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning (V2V)		X			
1.2	Cooperative lane change		X			
1.3	See through view for safe automated overtake		X			
2.1	Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control		X	X		eMBB service in mobile environment
2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur		X			
3.1	Sensor info sharing		X			
3.2	Connected maintenance		X			
3.3	VRU collision avoidance		X			
4.1	360o immersive multi-user gaming on the go			X		
4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go			X		
5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross-border logistics	X	X			
5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight	X	X	X		
5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation		X	X		

2.2.1.2 *Mobility*

Applications presented in Table 3 are all working in a mobile environment. However, mobility is handled differently in the case of macro and micro cellular networks.

- **Nomadicy** is often the only mobility scheme supported on micro cellular networks. In the case of CAM, the micro cell is moving and the user/vehicle registers on the network on a case-by-case basis.
- **True mobility** is supported on macro cellular networks. The user/vehicle registers on the network and uses different network resources depending on its position. The service is uninterrupted during the handover and the position of the user is known (except when in power off state).
- **Roaming** is supported between cellular networks. When the user/vehicle changes network, it registers on the new network. In most of these cases, service interruption occurs.

It must be noted that some applications, like mMTC, do not require the support of any nomadicy or mobility scheme.

CAM applications can take advantage of advanced registration mechanisms offered by the 5G macro layer to increase security, including authentication, positioning, etc. Contrary to nano or micro cells which move along with the car, macro cells are fixed. Cars are attached to different cells when they move. A true mobility scheme with the support of handovers is required. Different types of handover exist:

- HO between cells;
- HO between base stations in the same network;
- HO between base stations in different network.

The last HO is often not implemented and replaced by roaming agreements between operators. In case of roaming, the service is interrupted and a registration to the new network is done. Cross border situations mostly imply roaming procedures.

2.2.2 Core network

The following details some key aspects of 5G core networks.

2.2.2.1 *Mobile Edge Computing*

Edge computing in telecom, often referred to as Mobile Edge Computing, MEC, or Multi-Access Edge Computing, provides execution resources (compute and storage) for applications close to the end users, typically at the boundary of operator networks.

Edge computing can also be placed at enterprise premises, for example inside factory buildings, in homes and vehicles, including trains, planes and private cars. The edge infrastructure can be managed or hosted by communication service providers or other types of service providers. Several use cases require various applications to be deployed at different sites. With such scenarios, a distributed cloud is useful which can be seen as an execution environment for applications over multiple sites.

The main benefits the edge computing solutions provide include low latency, high bandwidth, device processing and data offload as well as trusted computing and storage.

The role of edge computing is critical. By 2023, 5G will make up around one-fifth of all mobile data traffic, where 25% of the use-cases will depend on edge computing capabilities. The majority of 5G revenue potential is expected to come from enterprise & IoT services, of which many will rely on edge computing.

For consumers, new virtual reality (VR) and gaming applications will leverage the improved user experience that edge computing can enable. Therefore edge capabilities will be a fundamental technology as part of a 5G infrastructure for any service provider.

2.2.2.2 *Network slicing*

Network slicing is the operators' best answer on how to build and manage a network that meets and exceeds the emerging requirements from a wide range of enterprises. The way to achieve a sliced network is to transform it into a set of logical networks on top of a shared infrastructure. Each logical network is designed to serve a defined business purpose and comprises of all the required network resources, configured and connected end-to-end.

Network slicing enables the most economical model to provide service differentiation and meeting end user SLAs. It facilitates the creation of new types of service offerings and supports different enterprise business models in a flexible way with a high service deployment rate. It is an enabler to generate more revenue for the service provider at a lower cost than with alternative solutions.

2.2.2.3 *Roaming*

Roaming is the capability for mobile subscribers to use the services offered by different networks when travelling across different countries. In roaming situations, the subscriber registers itself to the visited PLMN and the visited PLMN returns this information to the home PLMN.

The roaming procedure involves authentication and registration. During the roaming procedure, the communication is cut, leading to a service interruption which is in the minute order of magnitude. Roaming can be considered as the main disruptive factor in cross border communication situations. Enhancement of

roaming procedures in 5G could lead to seamless network change when crossing borders even for critical CAM applications.

From the end user point of view, roaming extends the service area of its home PLMN in a quasi-transparent manner, particularly in Europe where regulations impose that communication in the visited PLMN are at the same price as in the home PLMN.

The importance of roaming is emphasized for voice/video telephony services because of the necessity to support incoming calls: the advantage of roaming versus using dual sim (one for the home, one for the visited PLMN) being that the incoming calls are routed from the home PLMN to the visited PLMN. In the case of CAM applications, roaming is necessary to ensure the continuity of the service in cross border situations.

2.3 Satellite communication networks

The Satellite communication (SatCom) systems englobes all the artificial earth satellite launched for the telecommunication purpose.

The telecommunication satellite can be launched in 3 main types of orbits:

- LEO (Low Earth Orbit): up to 2000 km;
- MEO (Medium Earth Orbit): from 2000 km to geostationary orbit at 35786 km;
- GEO (Geostationary Orbit): 35786 km.

2.3.1 Satellite resources and characteristics

The satellite systems are defined by the main following characteristics:

1) Coverage

Telecommunication Satellites, in particular GEO satellites, offer a large coverage of earth. Three GEO satellites are enough to provide a near global coverage of the earth.

Figure 3. Satellite Global Coverage (source Inmarsat)

In order to improve the quality of service, the coverage is in most of the cases (e.g. for GEO and MEO based systems) focused on a specific area and several satellites are used to provide the desired service.

2) Capacity

The capacity of SatCom systems is provided in number of transponders, carrier bandwidth (MHz) or sometimes directly in data rate (Mbps). One of the key challenges of satellite system has always been the increase of the capacity with disruptive technologies and the efficient allocation of this capacity to meet service need.

Today HTS (High Throughput Satellite) and VHTS (Very HTS) allow higher satellite capacity systems, up to 1Tb satellite and more flexible resources allocation possibilities.

3) Availability

Availability of the satellite network is affected by propagation conditions. In addition to free space losses, the link budget must take into account rain and cloud attenuation. This is particularly important for high frequency bands like Ku and Ka suffer more from rain fading than L, S or C bands. The performances of satellite networks are different under clear sky conditions and rain conditions. As a consequence, the availability of a service will only be granted with a certain level of probability corresponding to the probability that the rain fade exceeds the limits.

Therefore, the key links between the satellites and their gateway locations are protected from rain fading by one or more of the following techniques:

- Uplink power control: increasing the transmit power when the link is partially attenuated;
- Gateway site redundancy: switch service to an alternative location when raining hard (either 1:1 or m:n protection);
- Locating gateways in locations where rain is unlikely: if the satellite coverage allows and a suitably connected location can be identified, this can offer a low cost means of mitigating rain attenuation.

In addition, most of the ground segment equipment shall monitor the propagation conditions and select the best modulation to exploit the satellite resources in an optimal way, while guarantying a minimum service grade even in poor conditions.

4) Latency

The latency in satellite network is directly impacted by the satellite orbit (propagation delay) and the network architecture. The propagation delay varies from 250 ms for GEO satellites to less than 60 ms for a MEO system at 8000 km and less than 10 ms for a LEO system à less than 1000 km.

2.3.2 Communication satellite services

- Mobile Satellite Service

Most Mobile Satellite Services (MSS) are provided by systems operating in L-band. MSS services are narrow band services (compressed voice, messaging) and Wideband services (up to 384 kbps). These services are provided either by GEO satellites like (Inmarsat or Thuraya) or by LEO constellations like Iridium or GlobalStar). The GEO satellites are characterized by the use of very large antennas that enable communication with mobile phones and IoT devices.

- Broadcast/Multicast

Broadcasting Satellite Services (BSS) is a unidirectional communication service provided by systems operating in various bands from S-Band to Q/V Bands. These services are provided by GEO satellites that cover a whole region. The reception requires a satellite dish or flat antenna which dimension depends on the latitude of the users and service area of the satellite

- Broadband

Broadband Satellite Service (FSS) is a bidirectional satellite service that is used to provide high speed internet access. The service is currently offered by GEO satellites, but several projects are on-going to provide this service with LEO constellations (OneWeb, Starlink).

2.3.3 Satellite and 5G integration and support of CAM services

Satellite communication networks are evolving and providing a novel stage of integration with 5G networks to support several use cases such as edge delivery, fixed backhaul services, broadband connectivity, mobile platform backhaul etc.

Several verticals can benefit from such integration and exploit satellite connectivity to enhanced use case feasibility and delivered service. Hence, to support CAM services and in particular in the context of 5G-ROUTES, satellite connectivity can provide the following assets:

- Provide coverage in cross-border context across different countries, in particular in the case or maritime border with ferries transporting users and components;
- Exploit the broadcast and multicast satellite to support edge computed CAM service running at the edge close to the user, by pushing appropriate software towards the edge and collect data for AI computing from different nodes;
- Support the service resilience in the case of failure of terrestrial system, either at the network infrastructure level or directly at the user level.

2.4 Network Performance

Network performance can be classified in different categories. Typical network KPIs are as follows:

- 5) Service area and percentage of population covered.

The targeted service area for terrestrial systems is often a whole country, although operators may decide to launch the service before having reached this objective (e.g. 5G hot spots). For satellites, the targeted service area is much larger, covering several countries or even a significant portion of earth.

The service area is attached to a frequency license. Operators cover in general most of the service area with the exception of areas which are difficult to cover (mountains, canyons) or not profitable which are called white or grey zones.

Cellular networks are interconnected, cross border service is obtained through roaming. However, in case of satellite networks, the coverage is very large, making cross border situations rare.

- 6) Network capacity.

This is a key indicator for the operator and the operators' revenue is a function of the total number of subscribers. On SoA networks, the penetration level of cellular networks is close to 100%. Each operator has a significant part of the market (>15%) and each network may support millions of subscribers. As with revenue, the cost and quality of the network is also a function of the number of users. This dimension is generally defined for each location/radio site. It depends on the traffic profile and is measured at the Busy Hour.

- 7) Network availability.

This KPI depends on the network load, meteorological conditions, equipment failures. Equipment reliability is often 99.99999%, which translates into hardware downtime of 5 min per year. But the targeted network availability is often much lower due to the difficulty to master the radio environment and the long time needed to recover after a failure. The targeted network availability is often between 98 and 99%.

Generally, these indicators are assessed/monitored throughout the network lifecycle which is not possible in laboratory conditions or field trials.

Service KPIs are used to evaluate the quality of the service from the network operator’s point of view. Each service type may have its own KPIs. For real time services, the main parameters are latency, end to end delay, jitter, max and average throughput and Bit Error Rate or Packet Error Rate.

Latency or round-trip delay is in most of the cases the time needed for a signal to traverse from an end user device to a server and back. It doesn’t include the voice, video or data processing done in the user terminal. IP Ping gives a rough estimation of this latency. In some use cases, the latency is counted in one direction only because the data stream is unidirectional (e.g. UC 1.3 see through view).

End to end delay or response time are the sum of network latency and voice, video or data processing. It is counted at application level, between the two communicating entities. In Real time applications, the end-to-end delay is minimized (around 200 ms), with similar values for network latency and data processing. On the other hand, non-real time application like web browsing, video streaming has much lower constraints, with responses time around 1 s; Maximum throughput is the maximum data rate that the user may use to transmit data over the network and the average throughput is the data rate that is granted to the user over a specific period of time. The average data rate must always be above the application needs for real time applications. In the case of streaming applications like Youtube, the data is buffered to cope with fluctuations in throughput. This buffering drastically reduces the real time constraint but increases end to end delay by several seconds.

Jitter is the variation of the delay. To cope with jitter, real time application buffer the signal, which increases the end-to-end delay and memory needed. Jitter is generally small (around 10-20 ms for radio, 100 ms for core networks) and transparent to the end user. In the case of cross border situations, it is generally not possible to compensate the jitter, which will lead to service interruption between 1 s for optimized networks to minutes for SoA networks.

Table 4 gives indicatives values of the performance of different commercial and experimental communication networks for real time services.

Table 4. Typical network performance (RT services)

Category	Type	Commercial				Field trial			Comments
		4G	5G	GEO Satellite	LEO satellite (1)	VTT test facility	Local field Trial	Large scale field trial	
Network	Service area	country	country	continent	continent	VTT site	Road test section	North Corridor (*)	(*) figures given assuming a mix of 4G and 5G network
	Coverage	99%	99% (*)	99%	99%	100%	80%	80%	(*) Using for example DSS (Dynamic Spectrum Sharing) 99% is theoretically possible, however it is highly unlikely that any country will aim for 99% 5G coverage in the near future.
	Cross border	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes (simulated)	yes	
	Number of subscribers	>1e6	>1e6	>1e5	>1e5	10	max 10	1e4	
	Simultaneous end users per cell	10 (*)	50 (**)	> 1000	> 1000	5	max 10	50	(*) Keeping in mind that there are both active (moving data or have data buffered) and connected (not moving any data on the cell) users. When the number of active users per cell reaches double digits, it could be considered an issue. (**) Not including IoT users.
	Availability	99%	99%	99%	99%	N/A	99%	98%	
Delay and jitter	Radio processing and propagation delay	40 ms	40 ms	300 ms	50 ms	40 ms	N/A	50 ms	(*) No data processing included.
	Network delay	15 ms (*)	< 5 ms (**)	50 ms	< 5 ms (**)	5 ms	N/A	80 ms	(*) Highly dependent on the operator.
	Network jitter (internet)	30 ms (*)	< 5 ms (**)	30 ms	< 5 ms (**)	< 5 ms	N/A	80 ms	(**) expected
Latency	Mobile to Fix latency	85 ms (*)	50 ms (**)	380 ms	60 ms	50 ms	30 ms (*)	50-150 ms	(**) expected
	Mobile to Mobile latency	80 ms (*)	40 ms (**)	700 ms	100 ms	80 ms	30 ms (*)	50-150 ms	(*) Highly dependent on the operator.
Cross Border impact	Service continuity	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A	Yes	No	
	Roaming duration	> 1 mn	0.5- 1s (*)	0 s (**)	0 s (**)	N/A (***)	0.5 - 1 s	> 2 mn	(*) expected (**) No impact of cross border situation for satellites because of the large coverage (***) roaming not supported
Throughput	Downlink (average per user)	10-20 Mbps	50-100 Mbps	2 Mbps (*)	4 Mbps (*)	20 Mbps	500 Mbps	5 Mbps	(*) assuming directive antennas in Ku/Ka band
	Uplink (average per user)	2.5 Mbps	25 Mbps	250 Kbps (*)	500 Kbps (*)	10 Mbps	50 Mbps	2.5 Mbps	(*) assuming directive antennas in Ku/Ka band
(1) typical for mega constellation									

Very low latency applications rely on micro cells. Due to the direct communication, the radio propagation time is reduced and there is no network latency/jitter. With micro cells, the latency could be around 10 to 20 ms. However, microcells are not totally safe and would still require support of the cellular infrastructure, e.g. for authentication and mobility management.

MEC are servers located close to the base station. They can be used for voice, video or data processing. The interest of having them close to the base station is that they are less impacted by the network latency and use the bandwidth more efficiently.

Reaching information delays below 10 ms is only possible with closed loop systems (optical radar, lidar).

Table 5 gives the network performance for non-real time service (i.e. SMS like service). To be noted is that SMS are less constraining than traditional voice and data services. Capacity is therefore not an important dimensioning factor of the radio access.

Table 5. Typical network performance (NRT services)

Category	Type	Commercial				Field trial			Comments
		4G	5G	GEO Satellite	LEO satellite (1)	VTT test facility	Local field Trial	Large scale field trial	
Network	Service area	country	country	continent	continent	VTT site	Road test	North Corridor (*)	(*) figures given assuming a mix of 4G and 5G network
	Coverage	99%	99%	99%	99%	100%	80%	80%	
	Cross border	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes (simulated)	yes	
	Availability	99%	99%	99%	99%	N/A	N/A	98%	
Latency	Transmission delay (*)	1 min	0.5 - 1 s	0.5 - 1 s	0.5 - 1 s	30 s	0.5 s	1 min	(*) one way
Cross Border impact	Service continuity	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A	Yes	No	
	Roaming duration	> 1 mn	0.5- 1s	0 s (*)	0 s (*)	N/A (**)	0.5 - 1 s	> 2 mn	(*)No impact of cross border situation for satellites because of the large coverage (**) roaming not supported
	(1) typical for mega constellation								

The one-way latency requirement for NRT services is typically between 1 and 2 minutes for 4G and around 1-2s for 5G and satellite networks.

3 Use Cases

The 5G uses cases that will be studied in the project can be allocated into 5 categories:

- Automated cooperative driving;
- Awareness driving;
- Sensing driving;
- Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go;
- Multimodal services.

These uses cases exploits different characteristics of 5 G networks and can further be grouped in

- eMBB
- URLLC
- mMTC

Table 6 shows the 5G characteristics applicable to each use case.

Table 6. 5G Networks Characteristics of 5G-ROUTES Use Cases

Category	UC ID	UC description	mMTC	URLCC	eMBB	Leader
Automated driving	1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning		M		EDI
Automated driving	1.2	Cooperative lane change		M		EDI
Automated driving	1.3	See through view for safe automated overtake		S	M	VTT
Awareness Driving	2.1	Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control		M		SWM
Awareness Driving	2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur		M		EDI
Sensing Driving	3.1	Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness		M		VTT
Sensing Driving	3.2	Connected Maintenance	M			TTU
Sensing Driving	3.3	Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Collision Avoidance		M		VED
Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go	4.1	360 immersive multiuser gaming on the go		M		BRA
Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go	4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go		S	M	BRA
Multimodal services	5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics	M			VEDIA
Multimodal services	5.2	5G-based Proactive and multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight	M		S	WINGS
Multimodal services	5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation	M			EVR

The following paragraphs detail the objective, specificity associated scenarios and requirements of each use case.

3.1 mMTC use cases

This category includes Use Cases that rely on the capability of 5G network to handle a massive number of devices, resulting in huge messaging processing requirement from the network.

The mMTC service is a messaging service. It must handle huge number of messages, but is not real time, thus leading to relaxed latency constraints (>150 ms).

3.1.1 Use case 3.2: Connected maintenance

The primary objective of UCC3.2 is to enable real time tracking of connected vehicles status from operation and maintenance point of view. Connected vehicular onboard diagnostics (OBD) system will be used to track vehicular parameters and status. Parameter collection and reporting system will be developed which will be combined into a preventive maintenance framework. This framework will combine OBD parameter collecting, OBD parameter reporting, parameter analysis and parameter prediction algorithms. TTU will create, install and configure controller device for collecting OBD parameters as well as communicating with cloud databases through Telia's network. Predictive maintenance algorithms will be developed in order to predict future behaviour of the connected vehicular. The framework will be made open in order to change parameters included in the analysis and prediction.

Initially the framework will be developed using ordinary vehicular with OBD connectivity. Predictive algorithms will be developed using Telia's existing mobile network and Cloud solution. The developed predictive maintenance framework will be transferred to autonomous vehicle when available and be adapted to their parameters and use the same methods for prediction.

3.1.1.1 *Use case objective and expected beneficiary*

Connected maintenance is a use case provided by the collection processing of sensor data within vehicles to monitor the health status of certain vehicular elements.

Objective is to allow connected vehicles to have connected and predictive maintenance. V2X communication will be used for sending vehicle sensor data to cloud databases where predictive algorithms will be used. This will enhance vehicles efficiency and provide higher safety as vehicles are better maintained. Their maintenance needs will be predicted, and servicing companies could be informed about the status.

TTU 5G-IoT test bed facility in Tallinn will be used to test basic connectivity and validate communication based on lab environment CANbus (OBD) interface with GPS sensor data.

The second step is to develop a controller to read vehicle OBD sensor data and send data through a 5G-IoT base station to a Cloud server. Database will be developed for sensor data storage. Data stored in the database will be used for data analysis and predictive maintenance. Cloud server will handle data storage and data analytics.

Multiple predictive algorithms will be implemented, and their efficiency compared.

Based on the sensor data and implemented algorithms a preventive maintenance framework will be developed through which the data collected from the sensors enable long-term maintenance and repair services. Emphasize on data analytics i.e., comparing number of methods for analysing the trends of parameters and then to predict early enough to avoid major malfunctioning.

Figure 4. Connected maintenance

During a border crossing, the connection to the network is temporarily interrupted. The service interruption is in order of magnitude of minutes on 4G networks, seconds on 5G networks. The connected maintenance system should be tolerant to missing maintenance messages

Car maintenance companies could be informed about maintenance status, their feedback could be included when handling vehicles maintenance needs.

This use case involves following stakeholders Citizens, car OEM suppliers, automotive maintenance, car OEMs

The end user is the most concerned by this use case which will increase the effectiveness of maintenance on his car.

3.1.1.2 *5G specificities*

This use case can run on 4G and satellite systems but takes advantage of the higher messaging capacity of 5G (mMTC service) to collect more data. In addition, the reduced cross border service interruption will reduce the need to retransmit maintenance messages.

Network slicing could be of interest to separate this application and its requirements from other services

3.1.1.3 *Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location*

The scenario for connected maintenance in TTU's 5G-IoT testbed will be used for

- Reading simulated sensor data, OBD-II reader is used to filter CANbus messages, the filtering helps to use defined number of parameters so that we do not overload processor which will be used behind the OBD reader.
- Transmitting sensor data through mMTC connection, ping tests will be used for testing IoT connection and also connection to the cloud server.
- Validating communication based on CANbus (OBD) interface with GPS sensor data

The scenario for connected maintenance in real network will be used for

- Extracting sensor data from a car OBD system during real driving, OBD message filtering used to collect defined number of parameters.
- Transmitting the sensor data through mMTC connection during driving, ping tests will be used for testing IoT connection and also connection to the cloud server, these tests will be used to do latency measurements.
- Storing sensor data in analytics database, sensor data filtering,
- Running real-time predictive analytics
- Estimating connected car maintenance needs
- Comparing number of methods for analysing the trends of parameters and then to predict early enough to avoid major malfunctioning.

The lab validation will necessitate

- OBD reader
- IoT infrastructure and terminals
- cloud servers

The field trial will require a 4G/5G or satellite infrastructure and compatible IoT terminals

3.1.1.4 *Associated Requirements*

- **Service requirements**

Number of messages per hour and per day

- Each car sends up to four messages per hour with maintenance information.
- The car is used two hours a day in average
- The number of messages per car per day is 8.

Density of cars

- Maximum Density of cars in urban areas. 0.01 car/m²

Reliability

- The number of lost messages should not exceed 5% of the total number of messages

Latency

- Latency is not critical. 1 hour is the target but up to 24 hours is acceptable.

Coverage

- 99% of roads

- **Technical Requirements**

Number of messages at Busy Hour / base station (RAN)

- Assuming a 5G cell radius of 300m (dense urban) and a density of cars of 0.01 car/m², the number of cars per cell is around 3000. The maximum number of messages at the busy hour in the cell is 12 000. This corresponds to a throughput of 3.5 kbps for 128 Byte messages (this could be increased significantly if acknowledgement or larger messages are required. This is compatible with 4G, 5G and satellite infrastructures. This constraint could be relaxed if the messages can be delayed until after the BH

Message processing time (server)

- The server will collect and process all the messages. For a large network with 30M of vehicles, if we consider that each vehicle generates 8 messages a day, the total number of messages per day will be around 120 M.
- Assuming 1s processing time per message, the server should be able to process up to 3600 messages per hour. This has a direct impact on the number of servers needed for the service: Around 350 if the network is dimensioned for one day of latency. If the server is dimensioned for the BH, the number of servers will be around 8400.

Reliability

- More than 95% of successful message delivery. This is not critical if acknowledgement and retransmission are used

Latency

- Latency should be less than 1 hour.

Service interruption time

- Less than 1 hour

- **Business Requirements**

Elaborated in the context of WP5.

3.1.2 Use case 5.1: Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics

The use case 5.1 will focus on supply chain transparency in multimodal transportation, which combines road and maritime transportation. The use case consists of two different cases (see Figure 5): in the first case the aim is to enable continuous connection for cargo monitoring IoT systems during the ship trip between Finland and Estonia. Second case will focus on mMTC, and study what opportunities 5G can provide for cargo monitoring and management on logistics nodes such as ports, where in relatively small area might be a lot of active IoT sensors.

Figure 5. Use case 5.1 illustration (source Vediafi)

3.1.2.1 *Use case objective and expected beneficiary*

Objective

- Case 5.1.A: To test capability of 5G networks for cargo IoT monitoring in logistics nodes (such as ports) Aim is to use 700 MHz + 3,5 GHz, and test IoT device with location information and some cargo status information (e.g. temperature, humidity, inertia, lighting, etc.) IoT device could be 5G/WiFi capable Vedia MTT150 CPE/gateway + CaaS IoT seal for cargo phase tracking. Field tests will be executed with Vedia devices and actual mMTC is tested with load simulation tests.
- Case 5.1.B: To enable connectivity for ferry transportation, so that road freight operator can manage own shipment also during the maritime transport. Aim is to use 700 MHz and Airbus satellite connection as WAN connections and connected cargo space WiFi or cellular repeater as LAN connection to enable IoT device control and management during the ferry trip. The truck will be driven to ferry and the same IoT devices will be used. Field tests will be executed with Vedia devices and actual mMTC is tested with load simulation tests.

UC 5.1 will focus on truck-ferry transport between Finland and Estonia, and in addition road freight transport in E67 (Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania). Connectivity and roaming issues between 4G, 5G and satellite networks during ferry trip between Finland and Estonia (65km) will be assessed.

The expected beneficiaries are freight operators and logistics service providers

This use case involves following stakeholders:

- 5G Routes team
 - Vediafi
 - Ericsson
 - Telia
 - Airbus
 - Tallinn University of technology
- Eckerö Line
- Truck company
- Ports

The continuous cargo monitoring will provide transparency information for end-users, but this use case is not specific to end users.

3.1.2.2 *5G specificities*

This use case will benefit of the full connectivity for IoT devices inside ferry and mMTC in ports

- In future each vehicle can carry plenty of IoT devices, which will monitor cargo condition and in logistics nodes there will be plenty of cargo vehicles/containers which will raise demand for mMTC
- 3,5GHz will be required at port to secure sufficient band width for mMTC.
- 700 MHz is interesting band for logistics, since it will enable relatively long and narrow but sufficient coverage for IoT services in ferry route

3.1.2.3 *Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location*

This use case is associated to use cases 5.1 A and 5.1.B (see above) which will be demonstrated in the large field trials. Load tests will be done separately with a load simulator.

The required infrastructure is composed of:

- truck-ferry transport between Finland and Estonia and related ports
- road freight transport in E67 (Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania)
- IoT devices will be connected to Vedia CaaS cloud system, from where data can be shared for external usage
- mMTC is tested with load simulator (tool will be decided later)

3.1.2.4 *Associated Requirements*

- **Service Requirements**

Message rate

- Each device is monitored 1 once per hour, 24h/24h 7day/week. This leads to 24 messages per day per device

Number of IOT devices

- Assuming 10 IOT devices per truck and 1000 trucks per harbour plus 10 000 containers, the number of IOT devices is 20 000.

Message processing time

- See § 3.1.1.4

Reliability

- See § 3.1.1.4

Latency:

- See § 3.1.1.4

Service interruption time

- See § 3.1.1.4

Coverage

- 100 % in harbour
- 100% along train track
- 80 along the ferry route

- **Technical Requirements**

See § 3.1.1.4.

- **Business Requirements**

Elaborated in the context of WP5.

3.1.3 Use case 5.2: 5G-based Proactive and multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight

This use case comes in two phases. The first phase focuses on the cross-border communication and provides mechanisms for notifications on approaching passengers and freight and assignment of necessary resources in the destination network (proactive resource allocation). In order to achieve this, it is important to leverage on heterogeneous inputs from vehicles, transferred goods and people and to propose prediction algorithms for predicting traffic in the destination network and plan accordingly the needed resources. Finally, it is important to include actions for setting-up and configuring the telecommunication network and any potential vertical aspects. Moreover, the multimodality aspect can be tackled in the second phase where unloading of freight from e.g. trucks and loading to ships can take place in addition to passengers’ movement. In this phase, there can be automated checking of freight (towards zero-touch), conducting logistics operations and informing authorities. Figure 6 presents an overview of this use case.

Figure 6. 5G-ROUTES Proactive and multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight use case overview

3.1.3.1 Use case objective and expected beneficiary

The **key objectives** of this use case are:

- To provide proactive and multimodal management of passengers and freight when crossing borders.
- To provide a pro-active resource allocation mechanism based on traffic predictions at the borders.
- To offer improved resource management capabilities at the border through customize predictive slicing & configuration

- To enable automated control and risk assessment on incoming passengers and freight, enhancing security and intelligence at the borders.

The main ***cross-border aspects*** of this use case are:

- Pro-active resource allocation takes place for the neighbouring PLMN, before the vehicles/passengers have crossed the borders (employing inter-PLMN communication). In this way the capacity of the target network is taken into account, and the service delivered to vehicles/passengers doesn't degrade when crossing the borders.
- Automated border control for passengers and freight is key for smooth multi-modal logistics operations on an international level. This use case will provide mechanisms capable of delivering such functionality at the borders, irrespective of connectivity restrictions (i.e. inter-PLMN functionality).

The ***key involved stakeholders*** of this use case are:

- Technology partners of 5G-ROUTES will leverage their expertise in IoT, RRM and analytics to design and develop algorithms for traffic awareness and prediction; procedures for zero-touch automated logistics operations; performance evaluation of provided solutions (field trials -simulations can also help to show scalability of solutions)
- Vendor(s) will provide necessary networking equipment
- Operator(s) will provide network coverage

The main beneficiaries are:

- The customs and public authorities that will have at their disposal an automated control tool for increased cross-border security regarding multi-modal traffic
- Operators that will leverage the enhanced capabilities of pro-active resource allocation and more efficient resource management at the borders
- End users such as passengers and logistics operators that will benefit from improved QoS/QoE at border regions.

Based on the above provided description this use case addresses challenges both from the network operator point of view as well as from an end-user point of view. While ***MNOs***, will benefit from the increased capabilities of pro-active dynamic resource allocation, network set-up and configuration in challenging cross-border environments, this use case also has significant benefits for end-users. ***Private citizens*** travelling with ***multi-modal means*** (ships, trains, vehicles) will experience increase network performance, and in parallel will be able to go through customs and inspection procedures much faster and more efficiently. Thanks to the automated control of incoming vehicles and cargo, this is also true for ***logistics operators*** moving freights across borders through a multitude of transportation modes.

3.1.3.2 ***5G specificities***

Some key parts of this use case could not have been realized without the advanced capabilities offered by 5G networks. More specifically 5G enables this use case as follows:

- Slicing capability offering differentiated QoS simultaneously towards different types of users: Thanks to the versatility of 5G networks different end-users (passengers, ships, trains, vehicles, logistics operators, etc.) may be served at the same time from a single 5G network. Slicing also offers extreme customization capabilities for dynamically configuring each slice, hence offering the capability to adapt to live traffic and network conditions.
- The mMTC functionality of 5G is the key aspect enabling this use case, as it is a prerequisite to collect a large amount of information from heterogeneous, fixed and mobile, sensors distributed along and

across the borders. As more and more vehicles/ships/trains will be equipped with a multitude of sensors, while passengers also create multiple traffic streams (smart-phones, tablets, smartwatches, etc.), the ability to efficiently collect and transmit information becomes critical, especially in cross-border environments.

3.1.3.3 Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location

For the local testing of this use case, prior to its deployment at the via Baltica corridor, the **CTTC Lab in Barcelona** has been selected. Two scenarios are identified of interest and are under investigation to be tested and validated in CTTC Lab in Barcelona.

Scenario 1: Multimodal network slice prediction, negotiation and management for passengers and freight when crossing borders. Figure 7 provides the functional overview of this scenario, including the participating components while Figure 8 provides the network-oriented description of the scenario.

Figure 7. UC5.2 - Scenario 1 functional overview

This scenario has the following attributes.

Service level functionalities:

- Traffic estimation (to dimension allocated resources)
- Service differentiation based on ongoing services (eMBB vs uRLLC, mMTC)

5G functionalities to be tested and demonstrated:

- Generation of Network slice requests based on the actual and predicted cross-border vertical requirements
- Network slice creation, deployment and management
- Network slice negotiation between a) two neighbouring PLMNs; b) verticals and PLMNs

Figure 8. UC5.2 – Scenario 1 network-oriented description

Scenario 2: Multimodal automated border control for passengers and freight. Figure 9 provides the functional overview of this scenario, including the participating components while Figure 10 provides the network-oriented description of the scenario. This scenario has the following attributes.

Service level functionalities:

- Risk assessment based on AI/ML analysis of cargo data, license plate, cross-reference of info, etc
- Preparation of multimodal transfer through the exchange of information (ETA, slice pre-allocation)
- Authorities interaction (customs)

5G functionalities to be tested and demonstrated:

- Real time analysis and prediction of border conditions on two sides of the borders. The outcome of this analysis is the generation of requests for network slice establishment on both PLMNs to support the means of border control.
- Establishment of appropriate network slices on both PLMNs for the communication between the means of border control (cameras, sensors etc.) and the Customs servers
- Possible migration of selected custom services from Cloud to MEC in case of special situations or emergencies
- Establishment of inter-PLMN Network slice for the communication between the two border Customs.

KPIs to be demonstrated and validated:

- Low slice deployment time
- Increase of operational efficiency of customs/borders authorities
- Decrease of security incidents in cross-border areas

Figure 9. UC5.2 – Scenario 2 functional overview

Figure 10. UC5.2 – Scenario 2 network-oriented description

In order to be able to implement and test the above-described test scenarios, the following equipment, SW/HW and components will be developed/deployed:

- **Cloud/Edge server:** Main AI/ML intelligence realizing the use case functionality. Application and user interface, aggregating/fusing heterogeneous information from distributed on-board and road-side sensors, smartphones, etc. processing and issuing i) directives towards CAM vehicles, ii) requests for slice and pre-allocation of resources towards neighbouring networks and iii) risk assessment results towards third party interfaces (e.g. customs authority, port authority, etc.).

- **On-Board Unit/OBU¹**: Comprising the “on vehicle intelligence”, aggregating on-board sensor data, transmitting it to cloud/edge server and receiving orders from the cloud/edge server
- **On-Board sensors**: Multitude of sensors to assist with traffic information estimation, vehicle status estimation and vehicle risk assessment. These sensors include (but are not limited to) ECU connector to receive vehicle information (speed, revs, temperature, etc.), IP HD camera, GPS, vibration, luminosity, CO₂, proximity, etc.
- **Road-side infrastructure & sensors**: A multitude of sensors will be used to collect information on traffic and incoming vehicles. All sensors will be housed in a Road-Side Unit (RSU) and will directly communicate with the Cloud/Edge server. These sensors include (but are not limited to) IP HD camera, proximity, infra-red sensors, motion sensors, etc.
- **Smartphone(s)**: Smartphone(s) will be used in order to track the location of pedestrians/customs agents in the test area and to interact with them via a user interface. Other potential uses of the smartphone(s) are not precluded (e.g. use of the camera, collection of additional information, video streaming). The location information of the pedestrians will be used as input for traffic estimation and resource pre-allocation.
- **CAM enabled Vehicles for trialling**: CAM enabled vehicle where the OBU can be integrated in order for the use case to be tested at the via Baltica corridor.
- **5G connectivity**
 - Testbed: The CTTC 5G testbed will be used for testing prior to the real-life deployment at the via Baltica corridor. The connectivity and functionality of all the use case components (OBU, RSU, smartphones, Cloud/Edge server) will be tested, as well as the proper functionality of the developed resource allocation and risk assessment algorithms.
 - Cross-border network: Two neighbouring 5G networks will be utilized to test the cross-border functionality of the developed functionalities.

3.1.3.4 *Associated Requirements*

The following general requirements are valid for the trial execution of this use case:

- 5G coverage throughout the trial paths
- Presence of MEC/Edge Servers in the trial environment
- 5G testbed and network to enable creation and real time update of network slices
- 5G testbed and network to enable creation and real time update of selected resources across the trial paths.
- Mixed presence of vehicles and pedestrians (e.g. at port) is required in order to assess the multimodal functionalities of the use case

For the execution of both scenarios described above, the following equipment will be used with the associated specific communication requirements:

- 5-10 GPS position signals representing cargo crates, vehicles, officers and/or pedestrians (low bit-rate, mMTC function). The source of the GPS localization transmission will either originate from dedicated GNSS chips mounted on vehicles and cargo crates or from smartphones that officers/pedestrians will be using. Transmission size ~ order of tens of kbps, transmission frequency ~ order of 10 Hz.
- Up to 10 distributed on-board sensors providing information about the vehicles and their cargo (low bit-rate, mMTC function). These sensors may for example transmit information regarding CO₂, temperature, luminosity, crate ID, etc. Transmission size ~ order of tens of kbps, transmission frequency ~ order of 1 Hz.

¹ Both the OBU and RSU will be equipped with chipsets enabling communication over 4G, 5G, NB-IoT and WiFi networks, allowing for benchmarking of performance

- 2 on-board proximity sensors transmitting information regarding the vehicles' distance to obstacles ahead or the vehicle ahead. Transmission size ~ order of tens of kbps, transmission frequency ~ order of 100 Hz.
- Up to 5 road-side sensors providing information about the vehicles approaching the border area (low bit-rate, mMTC function). These sensors may for example transmit information regarding license plate, number of vehicles passed, velocity, etc. Transmission size ~ order of tens of kbps, transmission frequency ~ order of 1 Hz.
- 2-4 IP HD cameras transmitting live video stream (UL) to the application server (high bit rate, eMBB function). These cameras can be either mounted on vehicles or on the road-side. Transmission size ~ order of 20-40 of Mbps per camera.
- 2-4 smartphones/tablets receiving the live video feed (DL) and sensor information, displayed via a monitoring GUI (high bit rate, eMBB function). These screens may either be mounted in the vehicles or help by officers/pedestrians. Transmission size ~ order of 40-60 of Mbps per smartphone/tablet.

The following KPIs are associated with the above-described scenarios and will be validated through the lab and field trials.

Scenario 1 specific KPIs

- QoS degradation < 5% during cross-border mobility
- Zero dropped sessions during cross-border mobility
- Low slice deployment time

Scenario 2 specific KPIs

- Low slice deployment time
- Increase of operational efficiency of customs/borders authorities
- Decrease of security incidents in cross-border areas

Overall Technical KPIs

- Throughput: 100 Mbps (DL/UL) per user
- E2E latency: < 100 ms
- Jitter: < 5 ms
- Mobility: < 200 km/h
- Reliability: 99.999% (RAN)
-

3.1.4 Use case 5.3: FRMCS telemetry operation

The Future Railway Mobile Communication System is the successor of the GSM-R communication system. The GSM-R network is a private network that enables personal and data communication between rail operators.

3.1.4.1 *Use case objective and expected beneficiary*

The **key objectives** of this use case are:

- ERTMS Level 2 and Level 3 systems to use 5G as medium to transfer telemetry data straight from train control unit instead of GSM-R.
- Railroad crossing warning equipment (barriers, lights) to be able to send their status to trains through 5G directly in case communication with central server is interrupted.
- Semaphores to be able to send their status to trains directly through 5G network with minimal delay rather than 100% through the distant server.
- Train telemetry information to be sent through 5G network at any time (constantly)

The main **cross-border aspects** of this use case are:

- If unified system is used, information exchange between train and railroad equipment directly (Machine To Machine) could be implemented to ensure secure train hand-over before train registers on the new network.
- Unified and standardized communication could ease the border crossing process: train operators and drivers will obtain the required driving permits easier.

The **key involved stakeholders and main beneficiaries** of this use case are:

- Railway operating companies to benefit from it through easier, quicker and unified railway traffic management system.
- Higher security level through faster data transmission to enable higher travelling speeds that will bring value to train operators as well.
- End customers to benefit through faster travelling speeds.
- ERTMS developers to be involved into this process. They are to provide necessary equipment (prototypes)
- UIC (FRMCS) should be involved into this process. They could see the possible 5G problems or benefits for the new FRMCS standard.

3.1.4.2 *5G specificities*

Today, ERTMS utilizes GSM-R as transport medium for telemetry data. All communication is routed to a single server belonging to railroad owner. Those networks are usually closed. Near-border railroad equipment should be able to communicate directly with in-train devices to enable seamless hand-over of trains between countries. FRMCS based on 5G could be able to enable that.

3.1.4.3 *Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location*

In-train controllers to be tested for direct communication with railroad equipment when network changes while crossing the border. Can be tested between two countries (Estonia/Latvia).

The developers of in-train control systems, as well as railroad safety/control equipment should be involved into this process. At this time, there is no particular vendor/developer chosen, so no specific information on the equipment to be used is available. The basic list should include:

- 5G-enabled in-train telemetry control unit
- 5G-enabled semaphore control unit
- 5G-enabled railroad crossing warning equipment control unit
- 5G-enabled radio block (and interlocking) center equipment

3.1.4.4 *Associated Requirements*

- **Service requirements**
 - Ultra-high availability (99.999%)
- **Technical requirements**
 - To be completed
- **Business requirements**
 - To be completed by WP5

3.2 URLLC use cases

This category includes use cases that rely on the capability of 5G network to send messages with a very small latency (typically below 200 ms). The number of devices/users is smaller than in the case of mMTC services, but is real time, requiring specific processing from the network.

3.2.1 Use case 4.1: 360 immersive multiuser gaming on the go

3.2.1.1 *Use case objective and expected beneficiary*

The objective of this use case is to

- Allow groups of up to 40-50 users to play Augmented Reality (AR) video games while on-route.
- Provide a fluid and identical AR scene status to all participants without the need to apply dead reckoning techniques that always lead to unfair game situations for users with higher latency connections.
- Get advantage of all users travelling on a same vehicle and path, in order to integrate all GPS and IMU data to increase position and orientation precision.

The objective is to keep the fluidness of the scene status for all users even when crossing borders: In 4G, when crossing the borders, users are roamed on the new network. This generally leads to a service interruption time. During the roaming, some players lose their connection and are not able to communicate with users that remain on the old network. When all users are roamed, a new gaming session must be launched. This situation will be improved with network slicing, leading to lower service interruption time

The expected beneficiaries are:

- Groups of travellers or individuals travelling by train, boat, buses, car or foot.

The involved stakeholders are:

- General public transport industry
- End users

This use case is directly driven by user requirements to have fairness when playing video games

3.2.1.2 *5G specificities*

5G can bring the following benefits to the use case

- Multiplayer games based on current networks always perform real time game synchronization locally, that way the whole game experience is less prone to lower latencies, while still providing a plausible behaviour. But nevertheless the use of dead reckoning techniques frequently lead to unfair situations that 5G networks latencies will remove.
- Not only reduced latencies but also minimal amounts of jitter will help removing the need to interpolate or extrapolate the scene status without affecting the visualization, allowing this way the exact same scenario during the game simulation for all participants in the multiuser experience.
- Improved signalling capacity in HO situations (train case)

360° Immersive Multi user gaming

Figure 11. 360° Immersive Multi user gaming

3.2.1.3 Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location

The different scenarios associated to the use case are

- Immersive multiuser gaming in CTTC 5G lab
- Large scale field trials

The infrastructure is composed of:

- Game Server
- Users’ smartphones
- 4G or 5G connectivity

3.2.1.4 Associated Requirements

- **Service requirements**

Latency

Latency should be below 0.5s

Reliability

This use case is not critical. In case of message loss, player position is not updated but the player should not be disconnected. See § 3.2.5.3 for details.

- **Technical requirements**

Latency

Latency should be below 0.5 s

Service interruption time

Tsi should be less than 1 min

- **Business Requirements**

Elaborated in the context of WP5.

3.2.2 Use case 2.1: Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control

The objective of the Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control use case primary is to assure and to enable a reliable exchange of road traffic status data between VRU’s, drivers and TMC through enhanced real-traffic video fed and 5G network. The real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control system allows

- first, the collection of information of the existing traffic management services to its further analysis.
- Second, the comparison between the existing TM systems and the improved C-ITS services which integrates the 5G network to collect and interchange data.
- Third, through an enhanced real-time traffic visual monitoring and the control of an intersection traffic, enable a safe passing for VRUs in a pedestrian crossing and a collision warning between vehicles.

As consequence, it is expected a boost of the automated driving due to the improvements of the C-ITS services produced by a more coordinated transport networks (e.g., enhancement in terms of vehicle position speed, driving trajectories, collision warnings, user comfort in traffic jams) and simultaneously the integration of novelty services for VRU’s, such as safe passing, to make them aware about the potential road hazards.

In cross border situations, the service must be provided over several networks located in different countries.

The expected beneficiaries of the use case are vulnerable road users, public authorities, drivers.

The involved stakeholders are traffic management centres, public authorities, 5G network operators

The safe passing case involves VRU’s; the improvements of the C-ITS services involve drivers and TMC’s

3.2.2.1 5G specificities (What can 5G bring to the use case)

This use case demonstrates the mMTC capabilities of 5G networks and takes advantage of lower latency than 4G in standard and cross border situations

Figure 12 depicts the overall 5G specificities of the system for UC 2.1

Figure 12. UC2.1 Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control overall Description

3.2.2.2 *Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location*

There are 2 scenarios associated to the use case:

- the efficiency scenario including efficiency services (like Traffic Light Assistance)
- the safety services that aim to prevent incidents at intersection level, protecting this way all road users.

The infrastructure supporting this use-case is:

- Fully equipped intersection with UTC
- Monitoring system based on AI analysis of video stream
- C-ITS infrastructure
- 5G networks

The UC 2.1 will be demonstrated at a complex intersection at Valga City, in which is required:

- 5G network coverage: 500 hundred meters around an intersection under test
- MEC server: due to the necessity to reduce the latency
- Traffic light phases information: it is necessary to understand how to get the data from the traffic lights, with the aim to generate the SPaT.
- Others:
 - SWARM analytics camera
 - 5G modem / router
 - 5G Android mobile device

3.2.2.3 *Associated requirements*

- **Service requirements:**

Response time

The response time of the system to new events should be around 1-2 s

Roaming

The service should support roaming in order to work in cross border environments. In this environment (like in Valga/Valka), the server is connected to both networks. It receives messages from all the users and cars located in the area of the intersection and dispatch the messages over the two networks.

Localisation

Users and cars must be localized at with a precision of 1m. This is feasible with Gallileo systems and could be combined with 5G localization techniques.

Interoperability

The service should work with legacy 2G, 3G or 4G systems but with degraded performances

Reliability:

The system is an additional security mean that complements existing systems. It is not critical.

- **Technical requirements**

Latency

Latency for an event to be received, processed and received by the user is not critical but should be as small as possible. A latency of 1-2 seconds is acceptable.

- **Business requirements**

Elaborated in the context of WP5.

3.2.3 Use case 3.3: Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Collision Avoidance

This use case aims at improving the safety of VRUs since their presence can be detected by vehicles, or infrastructure sensors which send the information to several other vehicles which may not be able to see the VRU at some point.

Information provided by roadside sensors with efficient timing and content will improve the vehicle perception and can be seen as additional sensors.

The raw data will be treated in vicinity of the road entities, i.e. in the MEC, to be quickly processed and the risk analysis will be shared with vehicles.

VRUs using smart devices, send their data (location, speed, type, etc.) to the cloud server, located in internet. This latter, having a global view of the network (vehicles, bicycles positions, etc.) will carry out a risk analysis operation and notify the concerned VRUs about hazardous situation.

This collaborative perception, i.e. information exchange among road participants, allows to enhance the usual perception capabilities of standalone users (vehicles, VRUs).

Figure 13. VRU schematic description

3.2.3.1 *Use case objective and expected beneficiary*

Objective

The use case aims the ultimate goal of “zero-fatality” of ITS on roads shared by vehicles, road side infrastructure and VRU.

This use case enables the exchange of raw or processed data gathered through local sensors or live video data among vehicles, RSUs, devices of road users (pedestrians, cyclist, etc.) and V2X application servers aiming at protecting VRU from hazardous situation.

Vehicles will be informed with the presence of oncoming VRUs and suggested the appropriate safe manoeuvres. In addition, the data related to VRU perception will be quickly processed and the risk analysis has to be made at the edge of the network.

Currently, the communication technologies like 802.11p and LTE cannot handle this big amount of raw data coming from perception sensors and are also not able to provide very little delay to ensure a rapid reaction of the autonomous vehicle.

By using 5G, vehicles, infrastructure and pedestrians are able to exchange and process information at very low latency, large bandwidth and very high reliability in order to avoid hazardous situations.

In cross border situation, the service must be available for the different operators located at each side of the border in order to ensure the requested continuity of service to protect VRUs

The expected beneficiaries are Pedestrians, Cyclists, Car manufacturers, Tier 1 and Tier 2 suppliers

The involved stakeholders are the City of Valga, Ericsson, Swarco.

3.2.3.2 *5G specificities*

The use of MEC technology allows local data analysis for faster decisions. MEC requires massive amount of data to be collected and dynamic map layers require low latencies to keep the database up to date.

Specifically, the system will showcase the added value of using 5G services like eMBB and URLLC technologies for advanced VRU protection use case.

3.2.3.3 *Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location*

3.2.3.4 *Associated Requirements*

- **Service Requirements**

- eMBB : To exchange raw sensors data between vehicles, infrastructures and pedestrians
- URLLC : Low latency exchange between road entities

- **Technical Requirements**

- 3G/4G/4G+ coverage
- 26 ITS-G5 RSU connected to the road side sensors and traffic lights (if it exists)
- Road side sensors (cameras and lidars) connected with sensor measurement units (object localisation and detection)
- Controllable traffic lights (if it exists)

- Mini base stations operating over 2.6 GHz (Band 38) and 3.6 GHz (Band 43) with six 5G small cells (RRU).
- Cloud and mobile edge servers
- User plane latency 10 - 50 ms
- Bandwidth 700 Mbps

- **Business requirements**
 - Estimate of capital cost per vehicle for the deployed system
 - Estimate of cost of purchased AV (market price)
 - Estimate of operating cost for the deployed system (per vehicle-hour or per vehicle-km).

3.2.4 Use case 1.1: Dynamic vehicles platooning

Automated vehicles driving together, dynamically form a group, moving at a very close distance from each other at harmonised speeds following a piloting vehicle. All vehicles in the platoon receive periodic data from the leading vehicle, in order to enable their AI-based OBUs to carry on platoon operations based on V2V communications and LIDAR detection system or environment perception system, thus enabling at least level 3 automation. This information allows the distance between vehicles to become extremely small (less than 5 meters), implying that the gap distance translated to time is in the order of a few tens of milliseconds for vehicles platooning at speeds allowed to drive at the given testing path section in cross-border highways, fulfilling safety requirements. Therefore, the OBU should be able to make calculations and apply them through MEC-enabled RAN stations at ultra-low latencies (i.e. less than 5ms with less than 10% jitter). Only the driver of the leading vehicle remains responsible for steering (level 1 automation), whereas the drivers in the following vehicles are relieved from driving, i.e. from both steering, accelerating, decelerating and maintaining the same distance (level 4 automation). 5G specificities

Currently, vehicle platooning experiments are done without network support. It is expected that the use of radio communication systems (4G, 5G, Satellite) will increase the level of security and foster the development of automated vehicles.

In cross border situations, handover and roaming are frequent, leading to a service interruption on 4G networks. This use case takes advantage of optimized roaming procedures on 5G networks to maintain the service even in cross border situations.

The use case could also take advantage of the reduced delay of LEO constellations versus a 5G networks in roaming situation.

3.2.4.1 *Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location*

This use case could be demonstrated in the racetrack local field trial with an experimental 5G network optionally complemented by a V2V communication system.

3.2.4.2 *Associated Requirements*

- **Service Requirements**

Security distance:

On the road, drivers must respect a safety distance representing two second of reaction time (the double of the average reaction time). The safety distance depends on the speed:

Table 7. Regulatory security distance

speed (km/h)	50	90	110	130
distance run in 2 seconds	27.8	50.0	61.1	72.2
regulatory security distance (m)	28	50	62	73

In the case of an automated vehicle, the reaction time is the result of the transmission time, the jitter and processing time. It depends on the type of network as shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Reaction time for automated vehicles

Reaction time for automated vehicles	V2V	Handover	Roaming	GEO satellite	LEO satellite	Human
Latency	20 ms	25 ms	25 ms	600 ms	100 ms	1-2s
Jitter	5 ms	50 ms	100-1000 ms	20 ms	50 ms	
Processing	80 ms	80 ms	80 ms	80 ms	80 ms	
Total reaction time	100-105 ms	105-155 ms	205-1105 ms	680-700 ms	180-230 ms	1000-2000 ms

The security distance depends on the speed and of the network architecture. The worst case is in cross border situation but represents still an improvement of 30% of the security distance, leading to safer cars and optimized road traffic. The best case is for the V2V architecture with an improvement of the security distance of more than 90%. In the project, we will rely on a 5G cellular infrastructure or satellites and will not use V2V communications. The objective is to improve of the safety distance by a factor 2 in cross border situations and 4 in normal conditions.

Table 9. Minimum security distance for automated vehicle

Minimum security distance for automated vehicles (m)		V2V	Handover	Roaming	GEO satellite	LEO satellite	Human
Speed (km/h)	50	1.5	2.2	15.3	9.7	3.2	27.8
	90	2.6	3.9	27.6	17.5	5.8	50.0
	110	3.2	4.7	33.8	21.4	7.0	61.1
	130	3.8	5.6	39.9	25.3	8.3	72.2

Reaction time

In order to meet the safety requirements, the total reaction time should be as small as possible and be in any case smaller than 2 s (human reaction time). According to Table 8, the reaction time is the sum of the transmission time, the jitter and the processing time.

For a 5G network, the reaction time is expected to be around 100 ms in handover situations and 1 s in cross border situations.

For a satellite network, the reaction for a LEO constellation is expected to be around 250 ms.

Position accuracy:

The measurement should deliver a relative position accuracy of 10% of the security distance.

- **Technical Requirements**

Latency

The latency should be as small as possible. It is expected to be around 25 ms for 5G networks, 100 ms for a LEO constellation.

Processing time

Processing time should be as small as possible. 80 ms is a target for processing, sending and receiving position messages.

Reaction time

In order to meet the safety requirements, the total reaction time should be as small as possible and be in any case smaller than 2 s (human reaction time). According to Table 8, the reaction time is the sum of the latency, jitter and processing time. The reaction time should be around 150 ms in handover situations and 1 s in cross border situation. 100 ms for a LEO constellation.

Throughput:

For platooning, the number of messages required to determine the position depends on the wanted position accuracy.

In roaming situation, the security distance varies between 15.3 and 39.9 m. The position accuracy should be 10%, so between 1.5 and 4 m. At 130 km/h, 4 m are covered in 110 ms. The minimum message rate is 9 msg/s. If we consider that each position report is 128 bytes (carID, time, latitude, longitude, altitude), the corresponding throughput is around 1,2 kbps.

If we want to support smaller security distances, for example between 4 and 10 m, the position accuracy is between 40 cm and 1m. At 130 km/h, 1 m are covered in 27 ms. The minimum message rate is 36 msg/s. If we consider that each position report is 128 bytes (carID, time, latitude, longitude, altitude), the corresponding throughput is around 4.6 kbps.

Reliability

Due to the real time nature of the service, packets cannot be retransmitted. The monitoring of packet errors includes the packet loss ratio, packet error ratio and successive errored messages. It is possible to cope with packet losses by increasing the number of messages, but it is not possible to cope with successive errored messages

In case of successive lost messages, the vehicle will fall back in degraded mode without network assistance.

- **Business Requirements**

Elaborated in the context of WP5.

3.2.5 Use case 3.1: Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness

Connected vehicles can enhance the perception of their environment beyond what their own sensors can detect so as to have a more holistic view of the local situation. In this regard, sensor info sharing enables the exchange of raw or processed data gathered through local sensors or live video data among vehicles, Road Site Units (RSU), UEs of pedestrians and V2X application servers, in order to achieve cooperative situation awareness. Vehicle uses its own sensors (e.g., HD camera, lidar), and sensor information from other vehicles, to perceive its environment (e.g., come up with 3D model of world around it) and safely performs an automated manoeuvre [3].

The Local Dynamic Maps in the vehicles (and at the infrastructure or the MEC) are continuously updated with information collected by other vehicles. In a cross-border situation, the service might be interrupted. The objective is to enable sensor info sharing for situation awareness even when crossing borders.

The expected beneficiaries are the End user (i.e. car drivers). The involved stakeholders are the automotive industry, telecom operators, standardization bodies. This use case requires standardization between different OEMs and sensor manufacturers to harmonize the protocols.

3.2.5.1 5G specificities

5G will bring increased throughput and smaller latency for this use case. This will improve the maintenance of Local Dynamic Maps, hence providing a longer electronic horizon than in the pure V2V case

Figure 14. Sensor info sharing

3.2.5.2 *Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location*

The different scenarios (if any) associated to the use case

- V2V, V2I combined with mMTC and URLLC
- potentially MEC can improve the electronic horizon, by providing a Dynamic map for the region. CPS messages are exchanged between vehicles, but when a vehicle has passed the object, which it has identified, it is not exchanged anymore with other vehicles. So, for roads with low traffic, drivers may not be made aware of oncoming objects.

The scenario is the same as the scenario for 1.3, but without the request of the driver for video: the decision (either automatic or driver decision) is solely based on the sensor and C-ITS information from the other vehicle. The use case requires:

- processed data: CPM
- other data: LIDAR? + data fusion.

3.2.5.3 *Associated Requirements*

- Technical Requirements
 - user plane latency: less than 10 ms [2], [3]
 - peak data rate up to 25 Mbps per UE [2]
 - support of high connection density for congested traffic (12000 vehicles/km²) [3]
 - positioning: 0.1 m [3] relative between two vehicles; high accuracy is required to avoid collisions.
- Service Requirements
 - service level reliability: 99.9 % [3]: very high, in order to guarantee QoS.
 - velocity: 250 kph
- Business Requirements

Elaborated in the context of WP5.

3.2.6 Use case 1.2: Cooperative lane change

Description: As part of the automated driving tasks, a vehicle should be able to apply manoeuvres in an automated manner, e.g. automatically change lanes in highways or at testing ground with required conditions, when appropriate, fulfilling safety requirements. For this, the interaction with the surrounding and the cooperation with other vehicles in the vicinity is of absolute importance, especially in the case of blind spots. The relative speed information of nearby vehicles is also considered to determine the risk factor and appreciate the safety of the manoeuvre, to avoid lateral or/and rear collisions with other passing vehicles. All nearby vehicles are informed about the intentions of the vehicle to perform safe lane change and reduce their speeds.

3.2.6.1 *5G specificities*

In this use case, each car has the knowledge of its environment. This includes other cars position (including opposite traffic), environmental information as road signs, presence of obstacle, traffic lights. Information are collected in a server and broadcasted over the network. The architecture is a multi-point architecture. Information processing is done in the MEC or internet server or/and in the cars. If the 5G infrastructure has an efficient broadcasting mechanism, it can be used to reduce the network load.

This use case requires special MEC and on-board processing with AI to analyse data and make the decision to change lanes

3.2.6.2 *Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location*

The AI algorithms and the selection of relevant parameters for the cooperative lane change will be validated through simulations in a lab environment.

Realistic parameters will be acquired by test drives on the race track. The parameters will be uploaded to a server via the 5G infrastructure and processed in real time. The data will be downloaded to each car via the 5G infrastructure.

3.2.6.3 *Associated Requirements*

- **Service requirements**

Security

The lane change should be as fast as possible but respect speed limits and regulation. Typically, overtaking should be done with a speed difference of at least 20km. At 90 km/h, it will take 10s to overtake a car driving at 70 km/h. There must be space to return to the original lane

Reaction time

See §3.2.4.2

Position accuracy

See §3.2.4.2

- **Technical Requirements**

Latency

See §3.2.4.2

Processing time

Processing time is an important contributor to the reaction time. It depends on the amount of data to process. A first estimation for the processing time is 500 ms for 10 cars.

Reaction time

See §3.2.4.2

Throughput

The uplink throughput is the same as for the platooning use case. The downlink throughput depends on the number of cars and the processing done in the MEC. The worst case is when all the processing is done in the cars. For 10 cars, the downlink throughput in that case would be 10 times higher than the uplink.

Reliability

See §3.2.4.2

- **Business Requirements**

Elaborated in the context of WP5.

3.2.7 Use case 2.2: Traffic jam chauffeur

3.2.7.1 *Use case objective and expected beneficiary*

- Objective

The objective of this use case is to enable the highest user experience by driving in the traffic jam, both, fulfilling safety requirements and user experience measures. This scenario tends to enable autonomous driving capabilities by utilizing 5G possibilities, while simultaneously engaging vehicle perception system and Drive by Wire control. In this scenario the goal is to enable smooth autonomous driving in traffic jam (high density low speed traffic) situation, by enabling lateral and longitudinal vehicle control, allowing accelerate, decelerate and shift a lane if it is necessary. In same time this scenario uses vehicle perception system to observe surrounding environment for the potential Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) as well nearby vehicles.

The following diagram shows the scenario footprint and involved partners:

Figure 15. Traffic Jam Chauffeur

What are the cross-borders aspects of the use case?

In the scope of cross-border scenario execution the user experience might be influenced by the fact of Ue (User Equipment) connection transfer from one MNO to other country MNO. This will lead to a critical delay and affect the scenario execution leading to an accident. The Use case will evaluate 5G capabilities to enable such scenario execution.

- Who is the expected beneficiary?
 - TBA
- Involved stakeholders
 - TBA
- How End-user specific is the use case?
 - TBA

Description:

This use case focuses on highly automated vehicles (up to SAE level 4) that would operate on motorways reaching the cross-border junction, in which a driver is not required for vehicular control. The scenario includes UC vehicles operating in roads shared with other testing vehicles, pedestrians and cyclists or its representation as the dummy targets [AL1] all following a designated route towards the border junction. The traffic jam chauffeur application would make automated driving in traffic jams or stop and go conditions more convenient. The application can steer the vehicle and its brakes in an automated way up to a specific speed limit, e.g. up to 70 km/h, monitoring at the same time the speed of the preceding vehicle and its surroundings through several sensor sources (e.g. to detect hidden objects and act accordingly), as well as the trajectories of nearby testing vehicles. The application integrates and makes use both of the lane assist feature of the vehicle to provide an active lane guidance function, as well as the traffic jam chauffeur for automatic braking and acceleration. The application would therefore enable lateral and longitudinal guidance, relieving also the driver from the responsibility for steering.

Note It is necessary to evaluate whenever real traffic vehicles or life pedestrians and cyclist could be involved in experiment, and how it is tackled by legislation. Usually dummy targets are used in industry conducting experiments for safety reasons.

3.2.7.1 5G specificities

- What can 5G bring to the use case

Primary 5G tends to enable low latency communication across connected devices, what will lead to a better safety and user experience. As a part of URLLC stakeholder requirement this scenario will evaluate defined KPI to desire expected goals. The URLLC could bring new user experience and enable fast and smooth driving in the case of traffic jam, by improving vehicle dynamic model as well better perceive high density environment.

3.2.7.2 Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location

The use case will be executed during local trial at the Bairiki racetrack. Meanwhile at the moment of writing this deliverable, location for the Large-Scale trials is being negotiated.

3.2.7.3 Associated Requirements

- **Service Requirements**

Security

- The scenario starts with approaching the traffic jam area by autonomous vehicle at the relatively high speed, i.e. 70 kph. In such a way there should be room to perform a successful exit from proceeding traffic jam lane. Human reaction time is needed to be considered to perform safe exit and prevent a potential accident.

Reaction time

- See §3.2.4.2

Position accuracy

- See §3.2.4.2

- **Technical Requirements**

Latency

- See §3.2.4.2

Processing time

- Processing time is an important contributor to the reaction time. It depends on the amount of data to process. A first estimation for the processing time is 500 ms for 10 cars.

Reaction time

- See §3.2.4.2

Throughput

- The uplink throughput is the same as for the platooning use case. The downlink throughput depends on the number of cars and the processing done in the MEC. The worst case is when all the processing is done in the cars. For 10 cars, the downlink throughput in that case would be 10 times higher than the uplink.

Reliability

- See §3.2.4.2

- **Business Requirements**

- The business requirements title related to the user experience KPIs. One of such KPIs tends to be an opposite value to an average system reaction time [1 / s] in the traffic jam during the scenario execution. This means that reaction time will affect to a total scenario execution time what tends to be reduced by utilizing 5G capabilities.
- As the second KPI what is affecting business requirement is average acceleration and deceleration in both axes. This means with the high acceleration it may raise bad user experience and scenario execution will not be smooth and definitely could affect end-user attitude to the technology. However low acceleration will contradict first KPI leading to a long execution time. The scope of this use case is also to find better distribution between these both KPIs.

3.3 eMBB use cases

This category includes Use Cases that rely on the capability of 5G network to offer broadband services in fixed and mobile environments. The throughput per user offered by the network should be above 10 Mbps in downlink and 5 Mbps in uplink

3.3.1 Use case 1.3: See through view for safe automated overtake

The main objective of this use case is to provide enhanced visibility of road awareness for safe automated overtake in order to prevent catastrophic head-on collisions during the manoeuvre. The objective is to support the automated vehicle in overtaking in mixed traffic on two-way roads (such as the E264 in Valga), where the vehicle's own sensors and the C-ITS messages cannot capture all traffic, through driver acknowledgement with the support of video.

- Sharing of pre-processed data, where objects are for instance extracted by an automatic object detection, is not sufficient, because the drivers' decision on a manoeuvre is subject to their driving capability and safety preferences (distance between cars, velocity of vehicles in oncoming direction). Sharing high resolution video data better supports drivers to make the manoeuvre decision according to their safety preferences. However, sharing low resolution video data is not sufficient, as obstacles are not visible and might get overlooked. Additionally, video data compression needs to be avoided as it leads to higher delays [2].
- The driver, sitting in an automated vehicle which is stuck behind a slower driving long vehicle, wants to overtake the vehicle in front, but does not have a clear view if overtaking is safe. The vehicle requests from the vehicle in front video streams in order to assess visually whether overtake is possible (e.g. real-time UHD video feed), and the driver confirms the intent to overtake, after ensuring that it is safe.
- Before performing the automated overtaking manoeuvre, the vehicle checks whether there are no conflicts, based on on-board sensors and C-ITS messages from other vehicles. This is performed through a series of computations, such as estimating the distance and path required to complete the passing manoeuvre, the trajectories of the vehicles, the estimated gap between the preceding vehicles at the end of the manoeuvre and the risk of a crash between that vehicle and a vehicle at the opposite direction in case their paths overlap (The same test can be performed prior to sharing the video, to inform the driver that it is not safe to overtake).

During a border crossing, the service is generally interrupted. The objective is to provide a service continuity in the see-through functionality even when crossing borders and ensure safe automated overtake even when crossing borders.

In intra network mobility situations, the video quality may be affected by handover procedures, leading to image freezing or increase of noise level. Handover between different networks causes disruptions in the service. Hence, to guarantee service continuity handover should be as fast as possible.

The expected beneficiary is the General public.

The involved stakeholders are Automotive OEM, Automotive suppliers, Telecom operators, Public authorities

The use case requires standardization, in order to work between vehicles from different manufacturers

3.3.1.1 *5G specificities*

5G radio offers a higher throughput than previous systems. This enables to increase the video quality. 5G core offers a better support of mobility that improves the video quality in handover and roaming situations.

New features in Release 16 and 17 allow to reduce handover time to nearly zero, e.g. "enhanced make before break handover"

MEC enables to reduce the End-to-end delay between UEs. The MEC:

- routes the messages between the vehicles with low latency (V2X Information Service, ETSI GS MEC 030)
- the presence of a distributed MEC-enabled 5G network can be beneficial not only to host computational power at the Edge for the data processing, but also to transfer real-time eMBB type video streaming, as well as perform video processing and orchestration analysis at the edge, so as to enable the vehicle to make an AI-based decision on the exact time for safe overtake. This requires low-latency reliable communication (URLLC) due to real-time aspects.

Figure 16. See through view use case

3.3.1.2 Selected scenarios

This use case is associated to the See through view scenarios in VTT's test facility and in the local field trial

It uses the following data streams:

- CAM messages from vehicles.
- service announcement of the availability of video stream (from leading vehicle)
- requests to initiate/end the video stream session (from follower(s) to leading vehicle)
- video stream (from leading vehicle to follower(s))

3.3.1.3 Associated Requirements

- **Service requirements**

End to end delay:

The see through view use case is a unidirectional transmission. The end-to-end delay is the delay between the image capture and its visualisation by the remote entity. It takes into account the transmission delays and the video processing time.

The E2E communication layer latency should be less than 50 ms [2][3][4]. The E2E delay at application level (from capture to visualization) should ideally be around 200 ms for a good user experience.

A practical measurement of the end-to-end delay in the case of the see through view case is to measure the difference between the number of the frame sent and the number of the frame received.

Table 10. Frame difference and E2E delay

Frame difference	E2E delay (ms)
1	40
2	80
3	120
4	160
5	200
6	240
7	280
8	320
9	360
10	400
11	440
12	480
13	520
14	560
15	600

Image quality:

The image should be displayed on a large display (17") with HD definition (1920*1080)@ 25-30 fps. The corresponding bit rate without compression would be 400 Mbps. However, with standard compression techniques like MPEG-2, the required data rate can fall down to 10-15 Mbps [2][3][4].

Reliability:

In cross border situations, the communication service will be interrupted due to the roaming process by around 1s. This makes it unusable for overtaking. However, this is not critical as the overtaking manoeuvre can be always avoided if the system does not work.

Set-up time

Set-up time is the time to discover the service provided by the vehicle in front and to establish the video. It should be around 1s

- **Technical requirements**

Video processing

The end-to-end delay (at application level) depends on the latency due to the transmission and the video processing.

We will only consider standard intra PLMN situation. According to Table 4, the transmission delay is expected to be between 25 and 75 ms, leaving 125ms for video compression and decompression. This is challenging for MPEG-2 video processing. Other compression techniques should be used as for example MJPEG which is less efficient in terms of bandwidth but has less delay (e.g. 720p video@30fps, MJPEG compression requires 10 Mbps)

BER/PER :

Compressed video is very sensible to transmission errors.

BER < 10⁻⁵

PER < 10⁻⁶ (QEF transmission)

Throughput:

The see through view use case requires a constant bit rate of 10 Mbps (uplink from the sender and downlink to the user)

Service discovery duration

The service discovery duration is the time needed for following vehicles to identify whether leading vehicle supports the service. It should be below 500ms.

Service establishment duration

The service establishment duration is the time to establish the see through video. It should be below 500 ms.

- **Business requirements**

Elaborated in the context of WP5.

3.3.2 Use case 4.2: 3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go

3.3.2.1 *Use case objective and expected beneficiary*

The objective of the use case is to:

- Allow reduced groups of individuals to participate on remote master class experiences through 5G connection, on-route, and fully immersive through head mounted display devices, and with remote immersive user interaction.
- Provide the required means for the presenter to be captured and inserted in real or virtual scenarios including immersive graphic elements to improve presentations and to enable presenter and final users to communication over specific graphics related to the explanations.

This use case is also possible in fixed environment (fixed mobile convergence)

Application fluidity and scene status should not be affected when crossing borders.

The expected beneficiaries are presenters and end users

The involved stakeholders are Telecom manufacturer and operators, Transport industry, SME

The use case requires a complex setup on the presenter side, including broadcast equipment and an increasing amount of hardware depending on the number of participants. On the user side it requires a graphics capable laptop and VR headset, although as new HMD's 5G compatible will be available, the user setup will consist just of them.

3.3.2.2 *5G specificities*

For a fluid and realistic integration of the presenter in the virtual scenario a high bandwidth is needed to send the presenter image with and high resolution, and a stable connection to avoid glitches or frame jumps. The 5G will allow to do that integration in the client side as well it will be done on the presenter side.

3.3.2.3 *Selected scenarios (provide justification) and use case location*

The virtual set setup will require standard broadcast equipment. The final user will require a high graphics capable laptop plus an HMD, although in future releases of HMD's it is expected for them to be higher performance and directly connected to 5G networks and therefore not requiring the intermediate laptop computer in charge of the video stream decoding and scene render.

3.3.2.4 *Associated Requirements*

- **Service requirements**

End to End delay

Around 200 ms for good user experience. See § 3.3.1.3 for details

Image quality

Image should be displayed on a High-Quality Virtual Reality headset or a large HD screen. See §3.3.1.3 for details.

Reliability:

In cross border situations, the communication service will be interrupted due to the roaming process by around 1s. This temporary service interruption is acceptable as the service is not critical.

- **Technical requirements**

Video processing

See §3.3.1.3 for details.

BER/PER :

See §3.3.1.3 for details.

Throughput:

See §3.3.1.3 for details.

- **Business Requirements**

Elaborated in the context of WP5.

4 Conclusions

5G networks will bring a significant improvement to the cellular offer, enabling to deploy new service like mMTC, URLLC and eMBB that cannot be offered by state-of-the-art 4G networks. In addition, the interconnection or even integration of satellite networks will increase the reliability and extend the coverage of the terrestrial networks. In particular, new evolution of the 5G technology enables to reduce the hand over time in roaming/cross border situations.

CAM use cases are particularly demanding in terms of performances: mMTC services require massive computation and signalling capabilities, URLLC services require specific optimizations from the Core and Radio Access Network and will take advantage of local processing capabilities provided by MEC servers. eMBB requires high data throughputs that can hardly be offered on 4G networks.

We have selected several CAM use cases that exploit these different aspects of 5G. These use cases are representative of the end users' needs in various domains, from automated cars to infotainment and railway applications. The work carried out in the project showed that the performances of 5G networks are sufficient but necessary to support our use cases.

This document is the initial version of the CAM use cases and will be updated by month M10. Further work will also focus on exploiting the synergies between use cases. The reduction of the number of use cases will facilitate the definition generic KPIs. Each use case will be illustrated by one or more scenarios to enlarge the test coverage. We will detail the test facilities and the test scenarios. We will finally define the service, technical and business KPIs to be monitored. Further work will detail the following elements:

- Test Facilities
 - CTTC 5G Lab
 - TTU 5G Lab
 - Paris Area (Satory)
 - VTT 5G test site
 - Local field trial
 - Large scale field trial
- Test scenarios
- KPIs
 - Technical KPIs
 - Service-level KPIs
 - Business KPIs.

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6 Annex I: Responsibilities Mapping

6.1 Responsibility matrix

Table 11 details, for each use case, the use case leaders and the partner contributing to the use case.

- Each company is identified by its code.
- The role of the company may be leader of the use case (Lead), contributing (c) or not involved

Table 11. Responsibility Matrix

Use Case Category	ID	Title	EEE	ADS	ADSF	PV	ATOS	BRA	CTTC	eBOS	EVR	ENIDE	CERTH	ILS	VED	IQU	LMT	SWM	TTU	VTT	TELIA	VEDIA	WINGS	EDI	
1 - Automated Cooperative Driving	1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning (V2V)							c								c		c		c			Lead	
	1.2	Cooperative lane change							c								c		c		c			Lead	
	1.3	See through view for safe automated overtake					c										c				Lead	c		c	
2 - Awareness Driving	2.1	Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control		c									c		c	c		Lead	c		c			c	
	2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur		c													c				c	c		c	Lead
3 - Sensing Driving	3.1	Sensor info sharing														c					Lead	c			c
	3.2	Connected maintenance		c								c	c						Lead		c		c	c	
	3.3	VRU collision avoidance													Lead				c		c			c	
4 - Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go	4.1	360o immersive multi-user gaming on the go		c		c	c	Lead			c											c			c
	4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go		c		c	c	Lead			c												c	c	c
5 - Multimodal services	5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross-border logistics		c		c					c	c							c			c	Lead		c
	5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight		c		c					c											c	c	Lead	c
	5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation		c		c					Lead											c			c

6.2 Participating Partners

Table 12. Task 1.1 partners

Company	ID
ERICSSON EESTI AS	EEE
AIRBUS DEFENCE AND SPACE GMBH	ADS
AIRBUS DEFENCE AND SPACE SAS	ADSF
AKCIJU SABIEDRIBA PASAZIERU VILCIENS	PV
ATOS SPAIN SA	ATOS
BRAINSTORM MULTIMEDIA SL	BRA
CENTRE TECNOLOGIC DE TELECOMUNICACIONS DE CATALUNYA	CTTC
EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED	eBOS
EESTI RAUDTEE AS	EVR
ENIDE SOLUTIONS .S.L	ENIDE
ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH
INLECOM INNOVATION ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	ILS
INSTITUT VEDECOM	VED
IQUADRAT INFORMATICA SL	IQU
LATVIJAS MOBILAIS TELEFONS SIA	LMT
SWARCO MIZAR SRL	SWM
TALLINNA TEHNIKAULIKOOL	TTU
Tehnoloogian tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy	VTT
TELIA EESTI AS	TELIA
VEDIAFI OY	VEDIA
WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IKE	WINGS
Institute of Electronics and Computer Science	EDI

7 Annex II: 5G Routes external stakeholders

7.1 Transport

7.1.1 Automotive industry

The automotive industry can be divided into the following major categories:

- **Automotive OEMs**

This category comprises the major automotive manufacturers for passenger cars - such as BMW, Daimler, PSA, Renault, The Volkswagen group - but also for trucks, busses and other speciality vehicles as well as companies that are customizing series production vehicles for specific purposes - such as ambulances, fire trucks, construction trucks, and many more. They all build, assemble and/or modify vehicles and deliver them to the end customers.

Their interest is to provide their customers with the vehicles that they request. As (mobile) connectivity is becoming more and more important, they want to implement the connectivity solutions that best fit their customers' wishes in the most cost-efficient manner. In addition, they are interested to generate additional business from connectivity solutions. Having established 2G/3G/4G LTE as the current baseline, they are very much engaged in transitioning to the emerging 5G solutions. They have established strong connections to mobile network operators through organisations such as the 5G Automotive Association (5GAA).

In Europe the Automotive OEMs are represented by ACEA 'European Automobile Manufacturers Association' (www.acea.be), whereas their research and development activities are supported by EUCAR 'European Council for Automotive R&D' (www.eucar.be).

- **Automotive Suppliers**

This category comprises the major automotive system level (so-called Tier 1) suppliers - such as Bosch, Continental, Delphi, Valeo, ZF - that provide major systems, subsystems and (mostly electronic) components to the automotive OEMs.

Tier 1 suppliers are interested in serving the automotive OEMs through customized and cost-efficient solutions. They want to be the preferred supplier also for the connectivity subsystems and to obtain competitive advantages through the rapid adoption breakthrough technologies. In addition, they are also interested in exploiting the benefits of increased connectivity and data availability on the other subsystems that they provide.

In Europe, the automotive suppliers are represented by CLEPA 'European Association of Automotive Suppliers' (<https://clepa.eu>), which is based in Brussels, Belgium.

- **Autonomous shuttles Manufacturers**

This category consists of a new emerging sector of the automotive industry; the manufacturers of autonomous shuttles – such as Navya, Easymile, Sensible 4, Irizar e-mobility, Google – that offer smart mobility solutions, usually electric, deployed mainly in urban environments with the cooperation of local public transport operators.

Their interest is mainly focused on the provision of public transportation solutions, mainly for door-to-door and on-demand services, complementing designated areas/routes of the local public transportation system. The business partnership frequently involves collaboration with cities, airports, hospital or university areas, as well as sports and recreational venues, where the deployment of autonomous driving solutions (usually of low speed) answers to a wide spectrum of smart mobility services. As 5G connectivity solutions could help make the operation of their shuttles more efficient (for instance through remote surveillance and troubleshooting), these manufacturers could become early adopters of these technologies.

Due to their recent evolution, no specific association exists yet; in Europe, such manufacturing companies have mainly evolved from the R&I (Research & Innovation) sector, by their direct or indirect (third party) involvement in European and national projects. However, the deployment of such fleets nowadays in quite a few European cities, demonstrates an insofar promising market penetration.

7.1.2 Automotive value chain

- **Fleet Operators**

Trucking and logistics companies as well as rental car agencies belong into this category of businesses that own and operate a (large) number of vehicles.

They are keen on the efficient operation of their fleet of vehicles and appreciate the benefits that connectivity can bring to their operations through increased availability of up-to-date data on their assets for instance for operational planning, predictive maintenance, troubleshooting, safety, serving their customers better and many other applications. In part they are also interested in increasing teleoperation, automation and autonomy in the vehicles.

- **Public transport operators**

This category includes public transport operators and the services they offer through their fleets (within 5G-ROUTES scope, bus and trolleybus fleets in specific).

Connectivity in public transport serves a major goal in two key areas; a) offering better transport services to the end users via use of crowd-sourcing and big data (i.e. improving schedules and routes, on demand operations) and b) deployment of autonomous shuttles integrated fully in local urban public transport operation, currently facing issues of accuracy in localisation and detection of blind spot hazards, resulting to low speed operations (at around 18 km/h), that are expected to be mitigated or even overcome by the deployment of the 5G technology (enhancing both safety and security).

In Europe, as well as Worldwide, public transport operators are represented by UITP 'Union Internationale des Transports Publics' (International Association of Public Transport) which is based in Brussels, Belgium (www.uitp.org).

- **(Local) Cloud/ IoT automotive suppliers**

This category includes major connectivity and data storage/ processing companies, such as Ericsson, NXP, TomTom, IBM, NEC, Google, who have in the past decade boosted their activities in the automotive sector, by providing local (in-vehicle) solutions offering a broad range of connectivity services between the vehicles and other connected objects via Cloud/ IoT; one major market segment is the IoT market, which is expected to be further expanded by the 5G technology deployment.

7.2 Standardization

7.2.1 ITU

The International Telecommunication Union (ITU is a specialized agency of the United Nations responsible for all matters related to information and communication technologies. Established in 1865 as the International Telegraph Union (French: Union Télégraphique Internationale), it is one of the oldest international organizations in operation. It is composed of 3 sectors

- ITU-T

The Study Groups of ITU's Telecommunication Standardization Sector (ITU-T) assemble experts from around the world to develop international standards known as ITU-T Recommendations which act as defining elements in the global infrastructure of information and communication technologies (ICTs). Standards are critical to the

interoperability of ICTs and whether we exchange voice, video or data messages, standards enable global communications by ensuring that countries' ICT networks and devices are speaking the same language.

- ITU-R

The ITU Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R) plays a vital role in the global management of the radio-frequency spectrum and satellite orbits - limited natural resources which are increasingly in demand from a large and growing number of services such as fixed, mobile, broadcasting, amateur, space research, emergency telecommunications, meteorology, global positioning systems, environmental monitoring and communication services - that ensure safety of life on land, at sea and in the skies.

- ITU-D

The Telecommunication Development Sector (ITU-D) fosters international cooperation and solidarity in the delivery of technical assistance and in the creation, development and improvement of telecommunication and ICT equipment and networks in developing countries.

7.2.2 ETSI

ETSI is a European Standards Organization (ESO) dealing with telecommunications, broadcasting and other electronic communications networks and services. ETSI supports European regulations and legislation through the creation of Harmonised European Standards.

Several technical committees are in charge of 5G or CAM related standardization work.

- SES (Satellite Earth station and Systems)
- ITS (Intelligent Transport System)
- TCCE (Tetra and Critical Communication Evolution)
- ARF (Augmented Reality Framework)
- F5G (Fifth Generation Fixed Networks)
- MEC (Multi-Access Edge computing)

7.2.3 ISO and CEN

ISO (International Organisation for Standardization) is an independent, non-governmental organisation with a membership of 165 national standard bodies. CEN, the European Committee for Standardisation, brings together the National Standardisation Bodies of 34 European countries. CEN and ISO have an agreement for technical cooperation. Standardisation work is performed in Technical Committees. Committees relevant for the work in 5G-ROUTES include:

- ISO/TC 204/WG 18 (Cooperative Systems) and CEN/TC 278/WG 16 (Cooperative Systems)
- ISO/TC 22 Road Vehicles: SC 31 Data Communication and SC 33 (Vehicle dynamics and chassis components), which also addresses testing of automated driving systems.

7.2.4 3GPP

The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) unites [Seven] telecommunications standard development organizations (ARIB, ATIS, CCSA, ETSI, TSDSI, TTA, TTC), known as "Organizational Partners" and provides their members with a stable environment to produce the Reports and Specifications that define 3GPP technologies.

3GPP is in charge of 5G standardization, covering cellular telecommunications technologies, including radio access, core network and service capabilities. It offers also hooks for non-radio access to the core network, and for interworking with non-3GPP networks.

3GPP technical specification groups (TSG) are grouped by technology:

- TSG RAN (Radio Access)

- TSG CT (Core Network)
- TSG SA (Service and Architecture)
-

7.2.5 C-ROADS Platform

The C-ROADS Platform is a joint initiative of European Member States and road operators for testing and implementing C-ITS services in the light of cross-border harmonisation and interoperability. Objectives include a common understanding of the functionality of Day 1 C-ITS services, the architectures and the responsibilities of the stakeholders. The C-ROADS platform has provided specifications for C-ITS Day 1 services (Hazardous Location Notification, Road Work Warning, Signalised Intersections). The message specifications are also being discussed with the Car2Car organisation.

C-ROADS is concentrated on mature communication methods for C-ITS and addressed both ITS-G5 and IP-based communication, for messages transmitted between back-ends of different organisations. The IP-based protocol is based on publish-subscribe mechanisms using AMQP Specifications.